

R2 – Curriculum Design of the Course “Blockchain for the Environment”

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Table 1: Deliverable Factsheet

Consortium

	Name	Short Name	Country
1	Aalborg University	AAU	Denmark
2	Tallinn University of Technology	TALTECH	Estonia
3	University of Limerick	UL	Ireland

Table 2: Consortium

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Statement of originality

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation, or both.

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List of Abbreviations

The following table presents the acronyms used in the deliverable in alphabetical order.

Abbreviations	Description
DLTs	Distributed Ledger Technologies
PBL	Problem-Based Learning
OERs	Open Educational Resources
HEIs	Higher Education Institutions
DBL	Design Based Learning
INATBA	International Association for Trusted Blockchain Apps
DAPPs	Decentralized Applications

Table 4: List of Abbreviations

Executive Summary

The BC4ECO Curriculum Design of the Course “Blockchain for the Environment” introduces an innovative, interdisciplinary curriculum that prepares students to navigate the complex and decentralised world of DLTs with an environmental focus.

The curriculum is structured into two modules with different knowledge levels:

1. **Basics of Blockchain for the Environment:** A foundational module designed for students from any academic background, providing an introduction to DLT and its potential to foster trust and accountability in environmental preservation.
2. **Leverage Blockchain for the Environment:** An advanced module aimed at students with a foundational understanding of DLT, focusing on environmental studies, design thinking, and the technical development of DAPPs.

The curriculum aims to foster creative, critical, and ecosystem-oriented thinking, equipping students to work effectively within diverse, problem-solving teams. It has been developed to address a range of academic backgrounds, ensuring accessibility to students with little prior knowledge of DLT, while also providing depth for those with technical expertise, particularly in computer science.

The course was successfully piloted through two summer schools, providing insights into the coherence of activities and learning goals.

1. Overview

1.1 BC4ECO Consortium

Aalborg University

At Aalborg University, all educational activities are centred around Problem-Based project work, based on a set of principles known as the Aalborg Model of Problem-Based Learning (PBL). This approach - integrated into all curricula at the university, has gained recognition internationally, and has attracted considerable interest from universities, researchers, and students both in Denmark and abroad. The Aalborg Model emphasises authentic problem-solving through self-directed group work and collaboration. It provides students with the skills to independently gain knowledge, develop competencies, and work with external partners to solve real-world problems.

Amalia de Götzen Associate Professor	Andy Peruccon Researcher	Luca Simeone Associate Professor	Ronald Chenú Abente Acosta Post-doc researcher	Patricia Csobánczi Research Assistant

Table 5: AAU Team

University of Limerick

Established in 1972, the University of Limerick is an independent, internationally focused university with over 17,500 students and approximately 1,800 staff. It is a young, energetic and enterprising university with a proud record of innovation in education and excellence in research and scholarship. The University of Limerick has been awarded a 5-star rating from the globally recognised QS Stars rating system (2023), placing it in the top 2% of all universities worldwide. UL's Kemmy Business School is now placed in the top 1% of business schools worldwide, having recently secured the “triple crown” of accreditation (EQUIS, AACSB and AMBA).

<p>Prof. Tiziana Margaria</p> <p>Professor of Software Systems at UL and Lero, the Irish Software Research Centre</p>	<p>Dr. Salim Saay</p> <p>Lecturer of Software Development and Software Systems Architecture</p>	<p>Dr. Roisin Lyons</p> <p>Lecturer of Innovation and Entrepreneurship</p>	<p>Ahmad Chaudhary</p> <p>Technical Officer, PhD student, professional services consultant.</p>

Table 6: UL Team

Tallinn University of Technology (TalTech)

Tallinn University of Technology (TalTech) is the only flagship in engineering and IT science and education in Estonia, providing higher education at all levels in engineering and technology, information technology, economics, science, and maritime. TalTech's mission is to be a promoter of science, technology, and innovation and a leading provider of engineering and economic education in Estonia.

Istemi Demirag Professor in Accounting	Viktoria Voronova Senior lecturer in environmental engineering and management	Sadok Ben Yahia Full Professor at the Technology University of Tallinn	Yaroslav Kobets

Table 7: TALTECH Team

1.2 Introduction to the Project

As we transition towards increasingly decentralised systems, the call for individuals to be self-sufficient and accountable is more pressing than ever. The INATBA¹ report underscores this, highlighting how decentralised technologies reshape society and the business landscape. Moving from a socio-economic context where third parties manage assets and data, to a new paradigm of self-custody and self-management, grants greater empowerment but necessitates heightened personal responsibility and socio-economic awareness.

Hence, future professionals must grapple with the strategic, organisational, and operational challenges DLT poses. This requires a blend of critical and creative thinking, a deep understanding of complex, decentralised systems, the ability to reflect on one's role in the ecosystem, and collaboration within interdisciplinary teams.

This result follows the paradigm of the novel pedagogical framework (see R1 report) and aims to craft a curriculum for an innovative cross-disciplinary course titled 'BC for the Environment'. It offers versatile delivery modes, including a hybrid approach using digital resources, a flipped classroom format for both in-person or independent study with videos to springboard engagement and discussion. While the title emphasises 'Blockchain' for broader public recognition, the curriculum encompasses the wider realm of Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT), extending beyond just Blockchain.

The curriculum is designed with two tiers: a foundational level and an advanced level. The initial module, "Basics of Blockchain for the Environment", introduces DLT and its potential as a catalyst for trust in environmental preservation. This is tailored for students with little prior knowledge of DLTs, irrespective of their academic background.

The second module, "Leverage Blockchain for the Environment", delves deeper into environmental studies, design thinking, and the technical intricacies of constructing Decentralized Applications (DAPPs). This module is geared towards students, particularly those in Computer Science, who already possess a foundational understanding of DLT.

¹ <https://inatba.org/>

By engaging with both modules, learners will cultivate creative, critical, and ecosystem-oriented thinking, along with honing their abilities to work effectively within diverse teams in a problem-based setting. This result not only advances DLT education for computer science students but extends its reach to those from various disciplines, introducing them to the transformative potential of DLT in making environmentally conscious decisions.

Ultimately, this course is poised to equip students with a profound understanding of concrete application areas. It's expected to have a lasting impact on computer science students, fostering a deeper grasp of Sustainable Development Goals, Environmental Engineering, and a heightened environmental consciousness. This, in turn, will better prepare them to navigate the complexities of decentralised technologies and environments, contributing towards addressing the pressing challenges of our environmental crisis.

2. Module 1 - Basics of Blockchain for the Environment

The Module 1, Basics of Blockchain for the Environment, was operationalised during the Copenhagen Summer School on 26-28 April 2023 (see section 4.1). In the following section, we will limit ourselves to describing the various modules and content presented.

As previously discussed, the first Module, “Basics of Blockchain for the Environment”, targets students with little to no prior knowledge of the related topics. In fact, it is an opportunity to present various aspects of DLT and, after presenting various cases and applications of Blockchain concerning Environmental Sustainability, it offers various design tools and canvases to develop scenarios where such a technology is applied conceptually. Tables 1 and 2 summarise the main topics addressed in this first module and the resource files that were used during the summer school.

Topic	Resource File
Intro to Environmental Sustainability	Module 1 - E-tool for learning Blockchain-MSW in Appendix 1 Copenhagen Summer School - Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in Appendix 2
Intro to DLTs	Copenhagen Summer School - Intro to DLTs in Appendix 3
Design Brief	Design Brief in Appendix 4
DLTs Examples	Copenhagen Summer School - DLTs and Blockchain examples A in Appendix 5 Copenhagen Summer School - DLTs and Blockchain examples B in Appendix 6
Design Activities	https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVMQIrYw0=/?share_link_id=302065665715

Table 8 - Summary of the module 1 topics and resources.

3. Module 2 - Leverage Blockchain for the Environment

Module 2, *Leverage Blockchain for the Environment*, is the advanced module, where more technical aspects related to DLTs are discussed. This second module is dedicated to computer scientists and Engineers, which are expected to have a basic level of programming skills. The module is introduced and described in detail in Sect. 4.2. Here follows the collection of links to the teaching materials and case studies.

Topic	Resource File
Blockchain Game	https://medium.com/predict/how-to-teach-blockchain-with-the-blockchain-game-44360c542c81
Environmental Sustainability	Environmental Sustainability - TalTech in Appendix 7
Introduction to Environmental Case Study	Case Study on Identification of Microplastic in Shannon River using SEM, Spectroscopy, and Machine Learning in Appendix 8
Thinking in Systems	Solving Wicked Problems: Design Thinking and Systems Thinking - AAU in Appendix 9
(Re)Introduction to DLT and Blockchain	Blockchain Concept and Example - UL in Appendix 10
Organisations using Blockchain - examples	Organisational Collaboration Using Blockchain - UL in Appendix 11
Case Study - Blockchain Example (Case Zero)	Vision Zero and Blockchain: Data-Driven Framework for Resilient and Sustainable Road Safety - TalTech in Appendix 12
Prototyping - Introduction to Visual Paradigm	Visual Paradigm - UL in Appendix 13
Introduction to UML Design Diagrams	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=WnMQ8HImeXc
Applied Blockchain Canvas	Applied Blockchain Canvas in Appendix 14

Table 9 - Summary of the Module 2 Topics and Resources.

4. Use of the Curriculum for In-Presence Workshops

The curriculum has been tested through two summer schools that will provide some initial understanding of the coherence of the activities and respective learning goals. In this

section, the two summer schools are detailed in relation to the activities carried out, the participants and the evaluation.

4.1. C1 Summer School in Copenhagen - April 2023

The Copenhagen Summer School event unfolded on the 26-28 of April 2023. This event helped the partners to consolidate the theories of teaching and learning applied within the Pedagogical Framework. The Summer School in Copenhagen aimed at developing both teaching modules and a Problem-Based working group with students working in groups to tackle one specific given brief. The workshop explored the use of distributed ledger technologies (DLTs) in environmental sustainability - specifically within the topic of Water Management (see Design Brief in Appendix 4); it involved problem-based learning activities where attendees gained critical knowledge and skills in this area through a connected learning environment that will favour group work and networked digital resources.

4.1.3 Audience

This Summer School in Copenhagen was specifically designed for students with little to no prior knowledge of DLT. It is accessible to learners from various academic backgrounds. We tried to gather Master's and Doctoral students with backgrounds in Design, Computer Science, Environmental Engineering, and ICT to participate in the 4-day workshop at Aalborg University in Copenhagen. Eventually, the table below (Table 3) shows the number of students and their provenance and background.

Group Type	Broad domain of study	Students Nr
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Aalborg University of Copenhagen	Service Systems Design	8
University of Limerick	Computer Science	16
Tallinn Technical University	Environmental Sustainability	9

Table 10 - Amount of students, provenance and background.

4.1.2 C1 Summer School - Making the Brief and The Call

This first step of preparation included various activities of brief definition, concept creation and the final launch of the call. Each partner was instructed to reach out to their own universities to gather students based on the criteria established beforehand by the consortium. AAU took the initiative of drafting the call that should have been handed out directly to the students, highlighting the dates, topic, learning objectives, and the financial aspects of the trip. Student emails were obtained by providing a Google Form, where students' initial knowledge on the topics (before the Summer School activities) was also recorded. This was done to gain a comparative analysis of the students' learning before and after school. The list of questions for the first Google Form is listed below.

- On a scale from 1 to 5, how confident do you feel in developing conceptual solutions involving DLT or blockchain technologies?
- On a scale from 1 to 5, how knowledgeable are you now about UN Sustainable goals?
- On a scale from 1 to 5, how knowledgeable are you now about the Design Process and methods?
- On a scale from 1 to 5, how knowledgeable are you about Environmental challenges?

4.1.3 Activities and Canvases

In the Copenhagen Summer School, the design process was structured in 2 parts:

- Workshop Setup
- Workshop Activities.

Both the setup and the activities (which summary can be found in Figure 1) have been facilitated through a Miro board, as it is possible to see in Figure 2

Figure 1 -Summary of setup and activities for the BC4ECO Copenhagen Summer School

Figure 2 - Miro board presented to the students before the Summer School activities

4.1.3.1 Workshop Setup

The workshop setup was developed through Miro, a platform for collaboration that has been used within the project both for internal management activities as well as for workshop facilitation. In the Miro board, we could highlight various materials that the students could check before attending the school in the hope that it could engage the students with the Summer School topics beforehand. In the setup, we took into consideration 3 aspects:

- The Resource Sheet
- The Scan Cards
- The Design Brief

Resource Sheet

The resource sheet is a document that should be given to all the students participating in the Workshop Activity session and those who will be engaging in the Teaching Activities. Based on the Teaching Activity the students will select (courses to present), we recommended filtering out specific themes and topics in the document in Figure 3 below.

GENERAL RESOURCES TO GET YOU READY

DESIGN

ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILITY

DLTs

click me / read me!

click me / read me!

click me / read me!

Glossary of key terms:

You will need to check this out throughout the design activities happening in this board!

DESIGN PROCESS
A design process is a structured approach to solving problems and creating new solutions through the use of design thinking. It typically involves a series of steps that designers follow in order to move from identifying a problem or need, to prototyping and testing potential solutions.

Distributed Ledger Technologies (DLTs)
DLTs are a type of technology that allows data to be recorded and shared across multiple participants of a network in a secure, transparent and decentralised manner. They work with consensus mechanisms and cryptographic techniques to make sure the data is validated and recorded in a tamper-proof manner without the need of a central authority or intermediary. DLTs are relevant in various fields due to their unique properties of decentralisation, security, transparency, trust & consensus and overall efficiency. One great example of DLT is Blockchain, and you can take a look at the various scan cards (*) to see many examples on how they are applied across 4 domains.

SCAN CARDS
Scan cards are typically used in a process called 'horizon scanning'. Horizon scanning is the process of exploring and identifying potential signals of change. It involves 'scanning' a specific domain and analyzing patterns and factors that are likely to impact the future. Scan cards, while being only one research tool among many, are useful because they provide a digestible format that help individuals and groups to capture the identified signals of change in an easy way. They are composed of four sections, a title, general contextual information, relevance, sources.

ECOSYSTEM MAP
An ecosystem map is a visual representation of the stakeholders and their relationships within a system. It shows the flow of resources, information, and value exchange among different actors in the ecosystem. It is used to understand the complex interdependencies and dynamics of the system and identify areas for potential intervention or improvement.

USER JOURNEY
A User Journey is a visualisation of the path a user takes to complete a specific task or goal while interacting within a specific product, service, system, or process. It is a step-by-step representation of the user's experience.

How Might We (HMW) questions
A How Might We (HMW) question is a design thinking tool used to frame a problem or challenge in a way that encourages creative thinking and idea generation. The goal of an HMW question is to inspire brainstorming and ideation by reframing a problem as an opportunity for innovation and exploration.

Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)
A Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) is a universal call to action adopted by the United Nations in 2015 as part of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development. It is a set of 17 interconnected goals aimed at addressing global challenges, such as poverty, hunger, climate change, gender inequality, and environmental degradation, to create a more sustainable and equitable future for all people and the planet.

SCENARIO
In design, a scenario is a narrative or a story that describes a possible future situation or context. It is a tool used to envision how people may interact with a product, service, system or processes in different situations or contexts. Scenarios help designers and other stakeholders understand the needs, expectations, and behaviors of users. They can be used in the early stages of a design process to explore and evaluate different ideas or solutions, and identify opportunities.

TRUST LOOP
A trust loop refers to a virtuous cycle of building trust between two or more parties by continuing participation in a system. For example, a business may provide high-quality products and excellent customer service, which increases customer trust and loyalty. In turn, the customer's trust and loyalty encourage the business to continue providing high-quality products and services, thus creating a virtuous cycle of trust.

LOOPHOLE
A loophole refers to a gap or weakness in the system that can be exploited to undermine trust and compromise the integrity of the ecosystem. A loophole can arise due to various factors, such as inadequate governance structures, inefficient monitoring mechanisms, or lack of transparency and accountability. For example, in a supply chain ecosystem, a loophole could be an unverified supplier or a lack of visibility into the sourcing and production processes. If such a loophole is left unaddressed, it can erode trust among the stakeholders and ultimately lead to a breakdown of the ecosystem.

INCENTIVE ALIGNMENT
In DLTs discourses, incentive alignment refers to the idea that different actors within a network or ecosystem have aligned incentives to behave in a certain way that benefits the entire system. Incentive alignment can help ensure the stability, security, and sustainability of the system by encouraging positive behavior. This creates a shared interest and it results in an increased trust, cooperation and efficiency.

RECORD
Within DLTs, a record refers to a digital entry that is added to a shared, decentralised database. Each record in a DLT system is timestamped and cryptographically secured, and once added to the ledger, it cannot be altered or deleted. This provides an immutable and transparent record of all activities on the network, which can be used for a variety of purposes such as auditing, compliance, or dispute resolution.

PROVENANCE
Provenance in this case refers to the origin and history of operations related to a record. It includes also various data on its creation, ownership and movement/evolution over time. Having provenance provides an auditable and tamper-proof trace of a record's past.

MOMENTS OF TRUST AND POWER/TRUST MECHANISMS
A moment of trust is point in time when a participant in a blockchain network must place trust in another participant. Several power/trust mechanisms (e.g. cryptography, consensus algorithms) may be used to help establish trust

VALIDATION
Validation between transactions in the context of distributed ledger technology (DLT) refers to the process of verifying the authenticity and accuracy of a transaction before it is added to the ledger. Each transaction in a DLT system must be validated by the network participants, who use consensus algorithms to reach agreement on the validity of the transaction. There are different ways for validating a transaction:

- Consensus validation:** This is the process by which nodes in a network agree on the validity of a transaction before it is recorded on the blockchain. This is typically achieved through a consensus mechanism, such as Proof of Work (PoW) or Proof of Stake (PoS), where a certain percentage of nodes must agree on the validity of a transaction before it is added to the blockchain.
- Smart contract validation:** Smart contracts are self-executing contracts with the terms of the agreement between buyer and seller being directly written into code. In this case, validation occurs when the smart contract is executed and the agreed-upon terms are met. If the terms are not met, the transaction is not validated and the funds are not transferred.

PROTOCOL
Set of rules that govern how data is transmitted over a network or exchanged between systems. A protocol can be thought as a language that systems use to communicate with each other. The design of a protocol requires to understand who are the actors involved in the transaction, types of data that will be transmitted, as well as the goals and requirement of the system as a whole

BLOCKCHAIN ATTRIBUTES
DLTs such as Blockchain, are characterised by several attributes. These attributes are:

- Decentralisation** - meaning that it is not controlled by any central authority; instead, it is distributed across a network of computer (nodes), each of which has a copy of the ledger.
- Permissionlessness** - it means that anyone can participate in the network without the need for approval. This allows for greater inclusivity and accessibility, and it reduces the barriers to entry for new users.
- Immutability** - meaning that once a transaction is recorded, it cannot be altered or deleted. Cryptographic algorithms ensure that the system is secured and make it impossible to tamper with the data once it has been recorded. This attribute makes the blockchain trustworthy and ensures that there is high accountability and transparency in the system.

Figure 3 - Resource sheet in Miro with video material and a glossary of keywords

Scan Cards

Scan cards are typically used in a process called 'horizon scanning'. Horizon scanning (Amanatidou et al., 2012) explores and identifies potential signals of change. It involves 'scanning' a specific domain and analysing patterns and factors that are likely to impact the future (ibid.). Scan cards, while being one research tool among many, are useful because they provide a digestible format that helps individuals and groups easily capture the identified signals of change. They are composed of four sections:

- Title.
- General contextual information.
- Relevance.
- Sources.

Signals of change are specific events or changes that are happening now and could potentially shape the future. A trend is a pattern of multiple signals pointing towards the same direction, indicating a potential future direction (e.g., various organisations worldwide use blockchain technologies to regulate waste management). A driver is a trend or a set of trends that significantly impact the future and can shape the development of other trends or events. In other words, a signal of change is a specific event, a trend is a collection of related signals, and a driver is a trend that significantly influences the future. We can think of it this way: A signal is smaller than a trend, and a trend is smaller than a driver.

Throughout this event, we wanted students who could interpret and create various signals of change to critically reflect on how they influence their design decisions based on environmental sustainability aspects. Considering their diverse background, they must understand how a specific signal (or case) can be relevant in their practice and how it would influence their group's decisions and future scenarios.

In Figure 4 below, there is a chance to see the version of the scan cards that we presented on the Miro board for the activities.

Figure 4 - Scan cards used in the workshop.

Design Brief

In the following paragraph, we will present the text we used for the Design Brief for the Copenhagen Summer School. During the design process of the brief, the consortium encountered some issues in finding a real case in the city of Copenhagen to attach the brief to. Therefore, the partners had to devise a strategy to replace a real case with a fictional one that could still create in the students a sense of a pressing challenge to be tackled. Considering the heterogeneous composition of the consortium, we relied on our Design, Environmental Sustainability and Technological expertise to devise an alternative brief that could suffice our needs. After a few iterations, we briefly mentioned that students were encouraged to challenge the initial structure provided in case they found it relevant for them. In Figure 5, it is possible to see the brief with its visual elements as it was presented to the students, and in the following, we present the text with the reflections given to the students.

Figure 5 - The Design Brief

Text

The River Blue is an excellent resource for the city of Louisville. It provides drinking water for its inhabitants while sustaining a diverse ecosystem of aquatic plants, animals, and microorganisms. During the summer, the river is also used for recreational activities and becomes an essential resource for local farmers who irrigate their crops. Following governmental regulations, a wastewater treatment plant collects and treats the wastewater from the city's municipal sewerage to cope with the city's ongoing industrialisation. Together with other industrial facilities, they influence the river's water quality. Local communities of volunteers organise themselves to collectively clean the river's banks from plastic and unsorted floating waste.

The city's recent development has led many industries, such as power plants and manufacturing industries, to use the river water for their cooling processes, textile production & finishing. Besides using the water for irrigation, the farmers employ it to clean fresh products (vegetables, fruits) before supplying the local markets. To worsen the situation, the pressure on agricultural production has led many farmers to use fertilisers and pesticides on their crops, carried by rain and irrigation to the nearby streams, further polluting the water. The intense and unregulated use of resources and rising concerns

related to seasonal droughts deteriorated the water quality. They reduced many recreation opportunities, posing a significant threat to the ecosystem’s health by making the water unsuitable for human consumption.

The list of stakeholders involved in the brief can be seen in Figure 6 below

Figure 6 - Actors involved in the given Brief.

Key considerations:

Overall, Distributed Ledger Technologies have the potential to create more transparency, accountability, and efficiency in the management of water resources and contribute to enhancing the water quality, making it more accessible to everyone while rebalancing the ecosystem. Be critical of adopting such technology within the brief, and try to challenge students’ biases and assumptions on the topic.

We've listed several questions that can be relevant to - and not limited to this case:

- *How might we create more transparent and efficient mechanisms for water allocation among industries that draw from the river banks to incentivise industries to adopt more sustainable water management?*
- *How might we monitor and track the discharge of pollutants into the river and incentivise sustainable practices among industries and farmers?*
- *How can we hold industries accountable for the unregulated misuse of the river banks while integrating strategies for regulation and non-compliance measures?*

- *How might we ensure rewards to those players in the ecosystem that encourage or work towards the adoption of more sustainable practices for water usage?*
- *How might DLT technologies create more sustainable and autonomous ecosystems incentivised by decentralised and transparent ways of doing?*

This brief only provides students with an initial challenge and some guiding questions on how to address it; nevertheless, we welcome groups to challenge the brief and take different directions if they are more comfortable. During the workshop, we welcomed the students to integrate it with other relevant perspectives. For example, we listed several stakeholders interacting with the ecosystem, but we told them to challenge them and create new ones if necessary.

During the first day of the workshop activity, we stressed how the goal was to become familiar with novel technologies, environmental issues, and different and innovative ways of tackling challenges and working together. We stressed the importance of not evaluating their ideas based on their accuracy but rather on how we will evaluate their critical thinking process and how they would work together in groups.

4.1.3.2 Workshop Activities

In the workshop activities, we relied on various design tools and methods that could facilitate the students throughout various steps before finding a conceptual solution to the given problem. Some of the tools we provided have been inspired by the Decentralised Method Sheet developed by Patara (Erdogan, 2018), which was covered by a Creative Common licence granting us the possibility to use and improve the tools. In the Miro board, we made sure to mention the creators of the tools whenever we used a tool corresponding to the given method sheet.

The following steps represent the various activities we conducted with the students during the Summer School days. The following activities have been conducted between lectures to ensure that the content provided during the frontal lecture matches the hands-on activities performed in the design process.

First activity: Icebreaker

Once the groups were formed (before the Summer School to ensure heterogeneity), we divided the students in groups and assigned them their tables. The icebreaker activity was the first encounter with the other members of the groups and was a chance for them to get to know each other better.

The key questions for the groups are listed in the Figure 7 below.

Icebreaker

Figure 7 - Activity 1 the Icebreaker

Second activity: Scan Cards inspiration

To familiarise students with examples that combine Blockchain Technology with Environmental Sustainability, we conducted exercises using the scan cards. We wanted to encourage the student groups to collaboratively analyze the significance of these cases, considering their relevance to their own design briefs.

Exercise: Take 1 scan card each (4-5 per group) and discuss it within the group.

Questions: Why did you pick it? Why do you think it is relevant to solve the challenge presented in the brief?

The examples of Scan Cards can be seen in Figure 8 below.

Waste Management

TITLE
Empowering communities & fighting plastic pollution: the Plastic Bank initiative

ABOUT
Plastic Bank addresses plastic pollution by creating a business model that incentivises local collectors to gather plastic waste where recycling infrastructure is lacking. Collectors exchange plastic waste at local centers for cash, digital tokens, or vouchers. The collected plastic is recycled into "Social Plastic," a socially responsible alternative which is sold to international companies. Plastic Bank has established recycling centers in Haiti and plans to expand globally. They use blockchain technology in collab. with IBM to create a digital reward system for collectors, to exchange plastic for goods. The aim is to transform plastic waste into a valuable commodity, benefiting both the environment and low-income populations.

RELEVANCE
Blockchain provides secure and transparent transaction recording, enabling secure digital wallets for earnings storage. This not only incentivises waste collection, but also creates economic opportunities in underserved communities. Corporations can also support environmental causes by purchasing recycled plastic through Plastic Bank.

SOURCES

RELEVANCE
The system is designed to improve the efficiency of delivery systems, greatly reducing the volume of exhaust emissions released into the atmosphere.

SOURCES

centralised delivery networks

ogy to create a decentralized last-mile delivery system, messengers directly in a peer-to-peer (P2P) manner without n reduces the need for large, centralized logistics networks, ient and sustainable transportation by reducing carbon emissions art contracts, Volt creates a flexible and efficient system for ig the need for human intervention. This can streamline the more efficient use of resources and reduced environmental

Figure 8 - Examples of Scan Cards used in the exercise.

Third activity: Ecosystem Mapping and Trust Loop Canvas.

At the beginning of the process, it is key to map and visualise the system involving humans and non-human stakeholders and their relationships and interdependencies. At the same time, it is key to identify the different trust loops that occur within the given system. Identifying loopholes is relevant to understanding how blockchain mitigates specific power dynamics within system relationships.

Instructions on the activity are noted on the canvas (Figure 9).

Trust Loop

INSTRUCTIONS

- 1) Take one or more interactions among 3 or more stakeholders in the ecosystem map and try to identify the trust loop mechanism in place. See the example on the side, and take a look at the glossary to have a more clear idea of what a Trust Loop is.
- 2) Define what is the story of the transaction/relation. Explain the specific interaction between the actors in the trust loop.

Example of Trust Loop

In this relationship between 3 actors, one of them acts as an intermediary to ensure the payment process to exchange the bank holds a fee just for acting as intermediary and offering the payment course.

Ecosystem map

GROUP NAME:

ECOSYSTEM MAP

With such a map, you should be able to visualise the system that involves various actors (or stakeholders), being humans, machines, non-human stakeholders as well as their relationships and interdependencies.

SECTORS (A, B, C):

3 different circles represent different stakeholders groups:

- A - Actors directly involved.
- B - Internal Stakeholders (directly engaged)
- C - External Stakeholders (indirectly engaged)

INSTRUCTIONS

- 1) What type of users and stakeholders are part of this ecosystem? Try to find them all and map them in the system. You can challenge the brief and find new ones if needed.
- 2) What are the relationships between users and stakeholders in the system? Try to find them and map them, considering their nature.
Example of simple interaction:
Some stakeholder might provide resources (such as water) to other stakeholders in the system, and they can get either money, or other documents in exchange.
- 3) Highlight the trust loop in the ecosystem. Focus on the relationships among some of the actors (start with 3, e.g. user, provider, mediator/intermediary). If we take money transactions we see 1 user sending money (\$) to another user, and the bank acting as intermediary for the transaction.

Figure 9 - Ecosystem Map and Trust Loop canvas

Fourth activity: User Journeys and How Might We Canvas.

After selecting a Trust Loop identified in the ecosystem map, mapping the journeys of the stakeholders involved in the system is relevant to understanding the touchpoints where intermediaries influence the journeys of specific actors in the system. The How Might We canvas would eventually help the students transform the loopholes identified before into possible design opportunities. Instructions on the activity are noted on the canvas (Figure 10).

How Might We - Canvas

User Journey Map

GROUP NUMBER:

USERS:

STEPS:

DESCRIPTION:

ACTOR 1:

ACTOR 1:

ACTOR 1:

INTERMEDIARY:

What are the moments of trust ensured by the intermediary?

What are the trust loopholes arising from potential mistakes or misuses of power held by the intermediary?

INSTRUCTIONS

- After selecting a trust loop of 3 or more ecosystem, define the journey steps & the intermediary among them.
- Fill out the canvas with a sketch on the
- Identify the main touchpoints / stakeholder and try to identify some opportunities overall experience.

Feel free to use as many steps as you want - 10 for the amount of actors and steps you want to - if you need more space you can take another can have several levels of details, feel free to go actions or just stay broad if you think it helps y

TO CONSIDER

1. What is the problem dynamic you are trying to solve?

2. Transform your problem formulation into a How Might We question

3. Use a dot voting process to select the top voted questions

Figure 10 - User Journey map and How Might We Canvas.

Fifth activity: Design the Protocol

After identifying opportunities for decentralisation, the protocol is a way to design the set of rules that are taking place in the blockchain and eventually define: the actors involved, the type of data transmitted, the goals and requirements of the system. With this tool, we encouraged students to follow the suggested Design Criteria as explained in the canvas' instructions.

Instructions on the activity are noted on the canvas (Figure 11).

Figure 11 - Protocol Canvas

Sixth activity: Check-in Presentation

At this point, we wanted to encourage and invite the students to present their findings and the status of their design process. The presentation did not take more than 10 minutes per group. Considering the collaborative nature of the challenge provided we paired groups as a way for each group to provide feedback to one another. Regarding timing, we envisioned a 10-minute presentation and a 5-minute where the opposing group would provide feedback.

Seventh activity: Ecosystem Map and Behavioural Principles of Influence

After designing the Protocol, the students were able to represent again the system where different actors are related to each other in a more decentralised and distributed way. The principles of influence helped the students think with behavioural principles that can be useful to reorient the behaviour of the stakeholders as a way to invite them to take part in the more distributed protocol governing the blockchain. Instructions on the activity are noted on the canvas (Figure 12).

Principles of Influence

PRINCIPLES	EXAMPLE	APPLICATION
LIKING People like those who like them	At Tupperware parties guests' fondness for their host influences purchase decisions twice as much as regard for the products.	To influence people, win friends, through similarity: create any bonds with peers, bosses and direct reports by informally discovering interests, praise, charm and disarm, make positive remarks about others.
RECIPROCIITY People repay in kind	When the Disabled American Veterans enclosed free personalised address labels in donation- request envelopes, response rate doubled.	Give what you want to receive. Lend a staff member to a colleague who needs help, you'll get his help etc.
SOCIAL PROOF People follow the lead of others	More New York City residents tried returning a lost wallet after learning that other New Yorkers had also tried.	Use peer power. To influence horizontally not vertically e.g ask an esteemed 'old timer' to support your new initiative.
AUTHORITY People defer to experts who provide shortcuts to decisions requiring specialised information	A single New York Times expert opinion news story aired on TV generates a 4% shift in US public opinion.	Don't assume your expertise is self-evident. Instead, establish your expertise before doing business with new team members or clients. In conversations before a meeting, describe how you solved a problem similar to the one on the agenda.
SCARCITY People value what's scarce	Wholesale beef buyers' orders jumped 600% when they alone received information on a possible beef shortage.	Use exclusive information to persuade. Influence and rivet key players' attention by saying for example just got this information today.

Reference: <https://www.derekchristensen.com/6-techniques-to-get-whatever-you-want/>

Ecosystem map

GROUP NAME:

QUESTIONS TO CONSIDER

Who runs the software that validates (mines) the new blockchain? What is the incentive to run this software?

How will the actors access and use the new blockchain?

How might the roles and incentives of existing intermediaries evolve?

What new stakeholders and incentives may join in the ecosystem?

What new value mechanism may emerge from aggregation of records?

What new applications may improve utility and usability?

What are the implications of such a standardised and open record-keeping system?

THINKING WITH BEHAVIOURS

Take a look at the table 'PRINCIPLES OF INFLUENCE', and try to imagine:

How does the new ecosystem affect the stakeholders' behaviour? Can you use some principles of behavioral design to re-orient the behavior of the stakeholders in your new ecosystem?

Figure 12 - Ecosystem Map (V2) and Behavioural Principles of Influence.

Eight activity: Scenario Canvas

Scenario is a way to critically reflect on possible consequences of specific design actions in order to imagine preferable futures that can address the given challenge. This exercise encouraged the students to crystallise their own ideas with a hands-on activity that can take the form of a drawing, a Lego structure, a role-played activity etc. In fact, we encouraged them to express their scenario by first exploring the canvas and secondly, by

using their own creative means in order to develop it and present it in class. This activity is the presentation of their solution and how it will influence future users within the given challenge.

Instructions on the activity are noted on the canvas (Figure 13).

Scenario - Template

GROUP NAME:

INSTRUCTIONS

- 1) Fill out the template by answering the questions. Try to build up your idea based on the process you followed so far.
- 2) Within the group, briefly sketch you idea and find innovative ways on how to present it. You can role-play it, visualise it, code it, craft it. Use your own unique capabilities to do it!

BC4ECO has received funding from the Erasmus+ cooperation partnerships in higher education, under grant agreement No KA202-HED-2020-003

What are the preferable future scenarios to address water management challenges in your new ecosystem?

How can you capture the emerging opportunities in a narrative format to inspire further exploration and decision-making?

Give it a title and a short description of your solutions

What does it solve?

Who does it involve?

How does it work?

Figure 13 - Scenario Canvas

Ninth activity: Presentation Canvas

The project partners prepared a presentation canvas beforehand. This slide deck summarised various topics the students should have covered throughout the pitch to be given as a final step of their design process.

4.1.4 Evaluation and Feedback

Eventually, the students presented their solutions. As seen in Figure 14, the students presented their concepts using the canvases and the creative artefacts we provided to present their solutions.

Figure 14 - Group 3 Solution draw in both canvases as well as with Lego bricks

To evaluate the learning from the students, we developed 2 different evaluation methods. The first one was meant to assess the knowledge acquired by the students through frontal

lessons and workshop setup (Figure 15); this evaluation activity was sent out to the groups of students during the last day of Summer School and it was meant to provide the students a reflection point on their learnings. The second evaluation was more general on the learnings and critical points of learning from the workshop activities. The partners drafted a Google Form that was sent out at the end of the summer school. When the students filled it out, we could evaluate and assess the efficacy of the various teaching and workshop activities conducted in Copenhagen. The list of questions that we addressed in the survey is listed below, while the data collected is reported in **Appendix 15.**

Post-event questions

Knowledge acquired in the domains covered during the event.

- On a scale from 1 to 5, how confident do you feel in developing conceptual solutions involving DLT or blockchain technologies?
- On a scale from 1 to 5, how knowledgeable are you now about UN Sustainable goals?
- On a scale from 1 to 5, how knowledgeable are you now about the Design Process and methods?
- On a scale from 1 to 5, how knowledgeable are you about Environmental challenges?

Reflection Section

The next section highlights more granular aspects of the workshop and helps us understand if new capabilities emerge from working through interdisciplinary environments.

- On a scale from 1 to 5, how important is applying a decentralised mindset in your study/future profession?
- Why?
- On a scale from 1 to 5, how relevant do you think a decentralised mindset is when addressing complex environmental challenges?

- Why?
- On a scale from 1 to 5, to what extent do you think that working interdisciplinary helped you better explore the brief you were given?
- Can you give an example of a fruitful interdisciplinary exchange you had during the workshop?
- Can you give an example of a challenging interdisciplinary exchange you had during the workshop?
- On a scale from 1 to 5, to what extent do you think scan cards for futures thinking helped you throughout the design process?
- How did scan cards and the scenario activity affect your design process?
- On a scale from 1 to 5, to what extent do you think behavioural principles affected your design process?
- How did behavioural principles affect your design process?

The final stretch

The next final 4 questions are meant to evaluate the event as an overall experience; the students' feedback will help us improve it for the next students who will work in a similar way, applying the same concepts to environmental challenges.

- What is the main lesson learned during the workshop?
- Can you name a very positive aspect of the workshop?
- Can you name a very difficult/challenging aspect of the workshop?
- If we could improve one aspect of the Summer School, what would that be?

GROUP:

Quiz

You can do this in groups

Which statements describe a type of ledger that users consider in Blockchain?

- Distributed Ledger
- Decentralized Ledger
- Both, A and B
- None of them

In a peer-to-peer architecture, peers can serve as:

- Customers
- Waiters
- Intermediate system or middleware
- Both, A and B

What is Gas in Ethereum?

- The cost of generating a correct block hash
- A currency of pricing transactions based on their computational complexity
- A measure of the number of nodes connected to the network
- Computing power in the network to secure hashing operations

What is a node in a blockchain?

- A type of cryptocurrency
- A blockchain
- A computer on a blockchain network
- An exchange

Who Created Bitcoin?

- Satoshi Nakamoto
- Bill Gates
- John McAfee
- Vitalik Buterin

What is the Proof of Stake protocol in Ethereum?

- A way to reduce forking, by rewarding orphan blocks
- A way to hide transactions from the main blockchain
- A method of trading Ether on a platform based on a distributed exchange
- The name of the main consensus protocol in Ethereum.

Figure 15 - Quiz to evaluate the learning of students

4.1.5 Learnings for the next Summer School

In general the students appreciated the possibility to participate in the summer school and the more technical students to be exposed to the design process and tools, nevertheless some of the sessions were perceived as too technical and higher focus on the environmental aspects was suggested for the next iteration. The students appreciated the interdisciplinary approach and to be exposed to different educations and perspectives while addressing the same challenge.

4.2. C2 Summer School in Limerick - September 2023

The 2nd Summer School was developed for students with an intermediate knowledge of environmental issues, design, sustainability and Blockchain. This module aims to address an environmental sustainability setting, applying blockchain techniques to establish a collective circle of trust and facilitate behavioural change and knowledge development. The summer school was held in the University of Limerick (Ireland) during the 18th to 22nd September 2023.

Figure 16 - Header for the BC4ECO Blockchain for Sustainability Summer School

4.2.1 Differences between the Copenhagen and Limerick Summer School

The second summer school targeted students with an intermediate knowledge of environmental issues, design, sustainability and Blockchain. In addition, a live environmental case study was utilised to give the workshop an enhanced contextual and experiential focus.

4.2.2 C2 Summer School - Making the Brief and The Call

Emails to staff and students of each institution were disseminated in advance of the workshops, giving students adequate time to consider international travel. A Twitter (X) account was set up as well as an Eventbrite booking page.

Upon registering their interest, all participants were emailed an itinerary and an information guide - see introduction below:

WELCOME TO THE BC4ECO SUMMER SCHOOL

WHAT IS BC4ECO?

BC4ECO is Erasmus+ project involving the University of Limerick, Aalborg University and Tallinn University of Technology. These institutions have come together to create an exciting new educational programme focused on the topic "Blockchain for Sustainability". To develop and pilot the BC4ECO pedagogy and curriculum, two international summer school programmes have been developed. Following the summer schools, the BC4ECO consortium will develop two online courses (MOOCs) for scalable user enrolment and dissemination.

Summer School / MOOC 1: IDEATION AND INNOVATION Students will learn and apply a fundamental knowledge of sustainability and Blockchain to develop novel sustainable ideas which leverage the power of Blockchain technologies.

Summer School / MOOC 2: ADOPTION AND APPLICATION Using an intermediate knowledge of environmental issues, design and Blockchain, students will address an environmental sustainability challenge - applying blockchain techniques to develop a collective solution.

SUMMER SCHOOL LOCATION

The Summer School will be held on the 3rd floor of the Lero Centre - located in the Tierney Building, University of Limerick, Dromroe, Limerick, V94 NYD3

HOW SHOULD I PREPARE FOR THE SUMMER SCHOOL?

In order to gain the most from our summer school, we would advise that you familiarise yourself with the following:

FUNDAMENTALS

- The Sustainable Development Goals (<https://sdgs.un.org/goals>)
- Understanding The Basics of Blockchain:
 - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=QphJEO9ZX6s>
 - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Helf3Ku8kho>
- The Blockchain Toolkit: <https://widgets.weforum.org/blockchain-toolkit/>
[we encourage you to use the glossary tool in this toolkit in particular]

- *The BC4ECO Pedagogical Framework - accessible online via Miro:*
<https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVPzfwzbs=/>

APPLIED CONTENT

- [*Blockchain Technologies as a Digital Enabler for Sustainable Infrastructure*](#)
- [*In battle against climate crisis, don't overlook the blockchain*](#)
- *Report:* [*Blockchain for sustainable energy and climate in the Global South
Use cases and opportunities*](#)
- *Article:* [*Davos 2023: Education is key to driving sustainability in blockchain
and beyond*](#)
- *Article:* [*Forget Crypto: How Blockchain Helps Enhance Supply Chain
Sustainability, Transparency*](#)
- *Forbes Article:* [*Could Blockchain Be Sustainability's Missing Link?*](#)
- *Deloitte Piece:* [*Is technology an enabler for sustainability? How blockchain
can be used across value chains to achieve sustainability*](#)
- *Youtube:* [*Unilever Pursues Supply Chain Sustainability with Blockchain*](#)
- *Youtube:* [*How Blockchain can combat Climate Change*](#)
- *Youtube - Data Conversation:* [*Sustainability through Trust: Sustainable
Supply Chain with Blockchain*](#)
- *Youtube - Webinar:* [*Webinar - Blockchain technology as a driver for more
sustainable business models*](#)

- Youtube: [How Shell Is Using Web3 And Blockchain For Sustainability And Energy](#)
- <https://datalion.com/dashboard-software-product/datalion-social-media-trend-analyzing/>

DEVELOPER TOOLS [not obligatory preparation for the Summer School, but encouraged]

- HYPERLEDGER: <https://www.hyperledger.org/>
 - <https://hyperledger.github.io/composer/v0.19/tutorials/tutorials.html>

COURSES [not obligatory preparation for the Summer School, but encouraged]

- Microsoft Online Blockchain Course:
<https://learn.microsoft.com/en-us/training/paths/ethereum-blockchain-development/>

WHAT DO I NEED TO BRING?

We would advise you to bring the following to the Summer School:

- Laptop (optional but useful)
- Refillable water bottle
- A coat
- Comfortable footwear

SCHEDULE OF EVENTS

DAY ONE

When	What
9.15-9.45	Opening remarks and welcome
9.45-10.30	Blockchain Activity
10.30-10.45	<i>coffee break</i>
10.45-11.30	Understanding Blockchain Technology - Prof. Tiziana Margaria
11.30-11.45	<i>coffee break</i>
11.45-12.30	Applying Blockchain Technology - Dr. Salim Saay <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Using Blockchain for national collaboration</i>
12.30-13.15	<i>Lunch</i>
13.15-14.00	Group Activity: Blockchain Discussion <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Students discuss the advantages and limitations of blockchain technology.</i>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Students share real-world examples of blockchain implementation in various sectors (from their existing knowledge).</i>
14.00-14.15	<p>Sustainability Spotlight</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>The Sustainable Shores Project</i>
14.15-15.00	<p>Case Study Challenge - Introduction</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Dr. Michela Ottaviani - Applied Case Challenge presentation</i>
15.00-15.15	<p>Group Work</p> <p><i>Initial planning, reading of materials, Q&A</i></p>
15.15	<p><i>Move to Bus</i></p>
16.30	<p>Bus to Ardnacrusha Power Station</p>
18.00	<p><i>Safety briefing & tour</i></p> <p><i>Arrive at UL or hotels.</i></p>

Table 11 - Day One Schedule of Summer School at UL

DAY TWO

When	What
9.00 - 9.30	Recap and Reflection
9.30- 10.30	Solving Wicked Problems: Design & Systems Thinking – Dr. Amalia de Götzen
10.30-11.00	coffee break
11.00-12.00	Case Workshop 1 (BC4ECO team) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Extended information and resources (databases etc.) · Mentoring and facilitating discussion. · Technical checks and software planning
12.00-12.30	Prototyping Tutorial - Dr. Salim Saay <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Visual prototyping to develop architecture
12.30 - 13.30	Lunch
13.30 -15.30	Guided Technical Tutorial for Blockchain Implementation - Dr. Salim Saay, Ahmad Chaudhary

15.30-16.00	<i>coffee break</i>
16.00-18.00	<i>Group Work</i>
18.00-18.45	Pizza & Team Check-ins <i>Presentations of progress to-date. Mentors provide support and feedback.</i>

Table 12 - Day Two Schedule of Summer School at UL

DAY THREE

When	What
9.00-9.15	Recap, Q&A
9.30-9.45	Presentation format overview
9.30-11.30	<i>Group Work</i>
11.30-12.30	Expert Blockchain Presentation <i>Applied Blockchain presentation 1</i> <i>Applied Blockchain presentation 2</i>
12.30-14.00	<i>Working Lunch</i>

14.00-15.30	<i>Presentations and feedback</i>
15.30-16.00	<i>Coffee break - networking and deliberations</i>
16.00-16.15	<i>Winner announced</i>
16.15-17.00	<p>Conclusion and Next Steps</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Feedback Activity; Closing Remarks</i>

Table 13 - Day Three Schedule of Summer School at UL

4.2.3 Audience

This Summer School in Ireland was specifically designed for students with some prior knowledge of DLT. It is accessible to learners from various academic backgrounds. We tried to gather Master's and Doctoral students with backgrounds in Design, Computer Science, Environmental Engineering, and ICT to participate in the 4-day workshop at Aalborg University in Copenhagen. Eventually, the table below (Table 5) shows the number of students and their provenance and background.

Group Type	Broad domain of study	Students Nr
Aalborg University of Copenhagen	Service Systems Design	3

University of Limerick	Computer Science	18
Tallinn Technical University	Environmental Sustainability	3

Table 14 - Amount of students, provenance and background.

This first step of preparation included various activities of brief definition, concept creation and the final launch of the call. Each partner was instructed to reach out to their own universities to gather students based on the criteria established beforehand by the consortium. It was possible to gather students' emails by providing a Google Form where we could also assess the students' initial learning (before the Summer School activities); this was done to gain a comparative analysis of the students' learning before and after school. The list of questions for the first Google Form is listed below.

- On a scale from 1 to 5, how confident do you feel in developing conceptual solutions involving DLT or blockchain technologies?
- On a scale from 1 to 5, how knowledgeable are you now about UN Sustainable goals?
- On a scale from 1 to 5, how knowledgeable are you now about the Design Process and methods?
- On a scale from 1 to 5, how knowledgeable are you about Environmental challenges?

The participants were also asked to respond to the following two questions in an open-ended form. The answers are reported in Appendix B.

4.2.4 Activities and canvases

The following is the order of activities which were carried out during the summer school.

Blockchain Game

Blockchain technology can be a game-changer for accounting, supply chain, banking, contract law, and many other fields. The Blockchain Game is a hands-on exercise that explains the core principles of blockchains and serves as a launching pad for a discussion of blockchain's real-world applications. Designed for non-technical audiences and can be used to spark a discussion in many different fields.

The Blockchain Game is a practical game and toolkit developed by J. Scott Christianson to teach core DLT concepts. Excellent as a fun and interactive way to refresh key concepts with a class.

A hands-on exercise centres around a blockchain for student grades. No computers. Participants are the computers and calculate blocks.

The game seeks to teach core concepts about a distributed ledger, but can be modified to take in whatever direction the educator wants (smart contracts, supply chain applications, etc.)

Figure 17 - The Blockchain Game

Thinking in Systems

This section of the summer school briefly introduced systems thinking and why this perspective is important in sustainability and environmental challenges. It highlights how designers' capabilities can be used to support a more systemic perspective on challenges and problems that are often wicked and without a single solution. This is particularly relevant for Computer Scientists and students with an IT background to understand how designers would work on a wicked problem and how then the collaboration between experts from different domains could unfold. The systematic design approach could enrich the understanding of the complexity of the problem at stake and, at the same time, help to define a portfolio of actions to be implemented. We recommend such an introduction to open up the problem space for the technically skilled students, who might already have a good grasp of the technology but might miss the more holistic perspective and the intricacy of the forces at play. **Slides in Appendix 9**

 [AAU - Systemic Design - Limerick 2023.pdf](#)

Introduction to DLTs & Blockchain

This section described in depth a specific case study where the blockchain solution is introduced in the context of vaccine supply chains. This is a complete case study on a topic that every teacher and student relates with (the authenticity of the COVID-19 vaccine from its production to the capillary distribution) due to the global pandemic. It is relevant because students need to see a full case study, including the implementation and evaluation, as this presentation and the journal paper illustrate the technical layers and the evaluation and discussion. **Slides in Appendix 10**

 [UL-Blockchain concept and example-TM .pptx](#)

Organisational Collaboration Using Blockchain

This section discusses the role of organisational collaboration using Blockchain. Blockchain technology is pivotal for creating distributed, collaborative organisations by ensuring secure, transparent, and efficient transactions. Its applications extend beyond

global commerce to include remittances, innovative business models without intermediaries, and governance services. Particularly notable is its use in the educational sector, facilitating secure, GDPR-compliant online education platforms. These blockchain-driven initiatives address both legal and technical challenges, promoting inclusivity and global education access. This section of the course showcases Blockchain's ability to transform organisational structures and foster international collaboration. **Slides in Appendix 11** BC4ECO - Limerick -SS.pptx

Intro to Visual Paradigm

This section examines the use of Visual Paradigm, with examples to follow. Visual Paradigm is a software development tool available online and for installation, it supports the management and design of software projects. It offers robust support for various modelling languages and frameworks such as UML, BPMN, and Agile methodologies. The tool aims to streamline software development processes with features like system modelling, project management, requirements gathering, code generation, and simulation. Targeted at software developers, system analysts, business analysts, and project managers, Visual Paradigm enhances team collaboration and facilitates the delivery of high-quality software solutions. Its user-friendly interface, extensive documentation, and collaboration features make it an ideal choice for organisations seeking to improve their software development practices through efficient design and project management.

Slides in Appendix 13 BC4ECO -Visual Paradigm -SS

Introduction to UML Design Diagrams

This section provides in a concise fashion some technical background relative to standard system and software modelling to those students who do not have a technical background. It is also useful to the students who have technical background, in order to refresh it and establish some common terminology to be used by the entire class during the solution design and modelling phase.

It covers a short introduction to

- Modelling data structures through the definition of metadata, the concept of types, basic and complex types, through simple examples and a basic introduction to UML class diagrams for simple classes (no relations, no inheritance)
- Modelling protocols, with UML sequence diagrams (based on the Message sequence charts standards of telecommunication systems)
- Modelling workflows and business logic in UML activity diagrams
- Modelling architectures using UML class and component diagrams

Applied Blockchain Canvas

Canvas tools are commonly used as a strategic management tool to quickly and easily define and communicate a business idea or concept. These usually consist of a one-page document visual that guides participants through the fundamental elements of a business or product, structuring an idea in a coherent way. The Applied Blockchain Canvas tool then, is a one-page canvas which explores a business or policy concept which utilises DLT's. The users of the tool can use this to ideate new ideas for the use of Blockchain, or to map an existing company/project. This approach facilitates exemplar case study exploration and ideation of new processes, by examining what is already in place, and proposing new areas for development.

Figure 18 - Applied Blockchain Canvas

4.2.5 Evaluation and Feedback

Participants were requested to fill a post-course survey following the Summer School. Results indicate a positive experience, a rise in learning about key concepts, and some suggestions for improvement of the course.

5. Did this workshop help you to understand the intersection of blockchain and sustainability?

[More Details](#)

● Not at all	0
● A little	0
● A lot	8

6. Rate your knowledge level about blockchain technology after attending this workshop

[More Details](#)

3.88
Average Rating

Figure 19 - Post course survey findings: Understanding and Knowledge

7. Rate overall experience of the social activities and excursions.

[More Details](#)

Figure 20 - Post course survey findings: Social Activities and Excursions

10. Rate the overall quality of the workshop materials, presentations, and facilitation.

[More Details](#)

Figure 21 - Post course survey findings: Workshop Materials, Presentations and Facilitation

<p>Describe the main benefits of using blockchain technology to address sustainability challenges.</p>
<p>Synchronising the overall process, Preventing Manipulation by involved entities, Security and Spread of Awareness</p>
<p>Transparency and scalability</p>
<p>Immutability and transparency as well as possibility for different shareholders to share data securely.</p>
<p>Transparency of data ,</p>
<p>The main benefit of using blockchain in addressing sustainability challenges is the fact that it can provide access to trusted, reliable data which cannot be manipulated by third parties. It also allows many citizens to have an easy overview and understanding of the real state of environmental issues.</p>
<p>Blockchain technologies help in addressing sustainability challenges by providing a defined structure of operation from conceiving to production.</p>
<p>Blockchain can very much improve security in terms of data recorded and thereby prevent tampering.</p>

Table 15: Feedback on benefits on using blockchain technology to address sustainability challenges

<p>Share any challenges or barriers you foresee in applying blockchain technology to sustainability.</p>
<p>Deciding the Entities involved and designing a sustainable architecture</p>

Awareness
Communication challenges regarding the blockchain can be a problem, because it requires some skill to understand how blockchain works and what are the opportunities provided by it.
The barrier could appear if there were certain elements of a sustainable concept which require lots of room for flexibility and iteration of data, as well as ethical and emotional understanding of actors included in the system.
Energy consumption and scalability

Table 16: Feedback on challenges or barriers foreseen in applying blockchain technology to sustainability

If you were devising a course to teach "Blockchain for sustainability" to a technical audience, what would you include?
More Focus on Block chain Architectures, Diagrams, Code and on consensus mechanisms
The relevance of theory with practical case studies are very important. I really liked the micro plastic case study and visit to the power station.
I would include detailed workshops on specific topics about blockchain.
About blockchain, advantages, using a blockchain where mining is not done, sustainability , awareness for sustainability , how blockchain is gonna help for sustainability

I would include practical, hands-on exercises about blockchain as great as the one with Roisin and an exercise which would make the students understand the systemic perspective of a concept they'd create so that their ideas are actually impactful.
Discussion on scalability and energy efficiency.
I would include a general idea as to how blockchains are perhaps built up.

Table 17: Feedback on what to include in "Blockchain for sustainability" course

What improvements would you suggest for future iterations of this workshop?
A longer duration and slow paced workshop
Maybe add another day and make it 4.
More activities with the group also after the workshop!
Every team presents every day , so that they can have feedback.
Maybe energizers in-between the lectures. Other than that, it was a really great workshop. Kudos.
Go a bit in detail in the lectures prior to the group task since some participants are entirely new to either the concept or application software such as Java as we used in the last workshop.
Perhaps have the course be a day longer.

Table 18: Feedback on improvements

Figure 22 - Visit at Ardnacrusha Power Station

4.3. Final considerations

The following considerations were provided by the extended BC4ECO team following the Summer school programmes.

- While we believe that the BC4ECO project and workshops were successful, extending the approved participant pool to those external to the three institutions would widen the potential scope and impact.
- It took a considerable effort to prepare for the Summer Schools, a wider residual of the material, beside the MOOCs is being envisaged.
- The premise of the project “Blockchain for sustainability” necessitates a diverse array of experts, which can be a beneficial and innovative opportunity to connect varied communities together, under a key environmental mission.
- Integrating topics from different disciplines, such as Blockchain and environmental studies, presents a challenging endeavour but ultimately leads to the resolution of real-world problems.

- This multidisciplinary approach not only fosters innovation by combining technological advancements with ecological insights but also encourages a holistic understanding of how digital and natural systems can synergize for sustainable solutions.
- Such integration demands a deep understanding of both fields, necessitating collaboration among experts who can navigate the complexities of each discipline while identifying intersections where technology can address environmental challenges.
- For instance, leveraging Blockchain technology to enhance transparency and traceability in supply chains can significantly reduce environmental footprints by promoting responsible sourcing and consumption.
- As we delve into these collaborative efforts, we unlock the potential for groundbreaking solutions that address pressing global issues like climate change, resource depletion, and biodiversity loss.
- This approach exemplifies how interdisciplinary collaboration not only enriches our problem-solving toolkit but also accelerates the pace at which we can apply innovative technologies for the betterment of our planet.

5. The next steps

The two summer schools provided invaluable learnings for the development of a full curriculum that will be delivered in forms of moocs. The next steps in the project include the development of two online (MOOC) modules that mirror the two summer schools. The consortium is now working on how to adapt the summer schools to be fully delivered independently through an online course. One of the goals of the project is to make the MOOC's available for other teachers and students to increase the impact. In supporting this endeavour, the project will also develop a teacher guide that will support teachers in adopting and adapting this curriculum to their classes and courses.

7. References

- Amanatidou, E., Butter, M., Carabias, V., Konnola, T., Leis, M., Saritas, O., Schaper-Rinkel, P., & van Rij, V. (2012). On concepts and methods in horizon scanning: Lessons from initiating policy dialogues on emerging issues. *Science and Public Policy*, 39(2), 208–221. <https://doi.org/10.1093/scipol/scs017>
- Erdogan, E. (2018). Design Thinking for Blockchains. A method for exploring decentralization. Medium. <https://medium.com/patara/design-thinking-for-blockchains-ded1d6cabe53>

8. Appendices

Appendix 1: Module 1 - E-tool for learning Blockchain-MSW

**BC4
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Module 1

E-tool for learning Blockchain-MSW

Dimitris Damigos
National Technical University of Athens
Viktoria Voronova
Tallinn University of Technology

TAL TECH

UNIVERSITY OF LIMERICK
OILSCHOOL LUMINIGH

TALLINN UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY

BC4ECO has received funding from the Erasmus+ cooperation partnerships in higher education, under grant Agreement No KA220-HED-2021-003

Blockwaste game

Can be divided into two parts:

- Blockchain- what it is and how it works
- Blockwaste- how the waste can be blockchained and what good does it bring

2

Blockchain

- Blockchain is the tech. Bitcoin is merely the first mainstream manifestation of its potential.” — Marc Kenigsberg.
- Blockchain is not:
 - **a programming language.**
 - **a cryptographic codification.**
 - **an IA or Machine Learning technology.**
 - **a Python library** or framework.

3

Blockchain

- “The blockchain is an incorruptible digital ledger of economic transactions that can be programmed to record not just financial transactions but virtually everything of value.”
– Don & Alex Tapscott.
- works as an **immutable record of transactions that do not require to rely on an external authority** to validate the authenticity and integrity of the data.
- Transactions are typically economic, but **we can store any kind of information** in the blocks.

4

Blockchain key concepts

5 key concepts:

- Cryptographic Hash
- Immutable Ledger
- P2P Network
- Consensus Protocol
- Block Validation or ‘Mining’

5

Blockchain ecosystem

6

CRYPTOGRAPHIC HASH

Hash is a cryptographic function that transforms any input data into a fixed-length string of numbers in a way-

- the result is deterministic: if you use the same input, the output value will be always the same.
- the conversion is one-way: you cannot reverse the function to generate the original input.
- The Blockchain nodes use Hash functions to create a unique identifier of any block of transactions. Every block includes the Hash value of the previous block.

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CRYPTOGRAPHIC HASH

Hello

SHA256 HASH

05ade08fcfb104f40b2536a14dfcd6e916d643f5cf8044b19028b607ae8f4908

IMMUTABLE LEDGER

- Since every block of the chain contains the Hash of the previous one, **it is not possible to modify any block without changing the entire chain.** Hence, the chain works as an immutable digital ledger.

9

IMMUTABLE LEDGER

- If an anonymous attacker removes, adds or modifies any transaction in the first block, the HASH#1 will change:

10

PEER-TO-PEER (P2P) NETWORK

- The Blockchain does **not need any external or internal trust authority**:
 - **Blockchain data is distributed among all the users.**
 - **they spread the information of any new transaction** to the entire network.
 - the chain since it is **not stored by an individual entity** but for an entire network of *node* users.

CONSENSUS PROTOCOL

- Users need to meet an agreement about the validity of the **chain** before adding more blocks.
- Every time a node adds a new block, all the users have to validate the block by using a common protocol.
- They use ***Proof of Work or Proof of Stake*** methods.
- The nodes **check that the new block meets the requisites** of their *Proof* method, **including validation for all the transactions** inside the block.

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CONSENSUS PROTOCOL

13

BLOCK VALIDATION OR 'MINING

- The act of **meeting the *Proof of Work* requirements for adding a new block**
- There are many different mining methods, as they are custom defined for the chain
- Once a 'miner' node finds the solution to the PoW problem, they add the block to the chain and **every other node check the validity of the PoW according to their Consensus Protocol.**

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Blockwaste example

	Block	Area	Householder	Total waste	Nonce (1-3)	a	b	c	Last two digits from prev. Hash	Hash	Divid 3
1											
2										212	
3	1	Red	ad59dn	25							

Hash = Nonce+a+b+c – Value of Last 2 digits of Prev Hash

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Blockwaste example, step 1: calculate a

1	Block	Area	Householder	Total waste	Nonce (1-3)	a	b	c	Last two digits from prev. Hash	Hash	Divid 3
2										212	
3	1	Red	ad59dn	25			87				

Hash = Nonce+a+b+c – Value of Last 2 digits of Prev Hash

Lookup table		Lookup table	
A	65	N	78
B	66	O	79
C	67	P	80
D	68	Q	81
E	69	R	82
F	70	S	83
G	71	T	84
H	72	U	85
I	73	V	86
J	74	W	87
K	75	X	88
L	76	Y	89
M	77	Z	90

Blockwaste example, step 2: calculate b

1	Block	Area	Householder	Total waste	Nonce (1-3)	a	b	c	Last two digits from prev. Hash	Hash	Divid 3
2										212	
3	1	Red	ad59dn	25		82					

Hash = Nonce+a+b+c – Value of Last 2 digits of Prev Hash

Lookup table		Lookup table	
A	65	N	78
B	66	O	79
C	67	P	80
D	68	Q	81
E	69	R	82
F	70	S	83
G	71	T	84
H	72	U	85
I	73	V	86
J	74	W	87
K	75	X	88
L	76	Y	89
M	77	Z	90

Blockwaste example, step 3: calculate c

	Block	Area	Householder	Total waste	Nonce (1-3)	a	b	c	Last two digits from prev. Hash	Hash	Divid 3
1											
2										212	
3	1	Red	ad59dn		2	82	65				

Hash = Nonce+a+b+c – Value of Last 2 digits of Prev Hash

Blockwaste example, step 4: calculate Prev Hash

	Block	Area	Householder	Total waste	Nonce (1-3)	a	b	c	Last two digits from prev. Hash	Hash	Divid 3
1											
2				25							
3	1	Red	ad59dn			82	65	25			

Hash = Nonce+a+b+c – Value of Last 2 digits of Prev Hash

Blockwaste example, step 5: calculate Hash

1	Block	Area	Householder	Total waste	Nonce (1-3)	a	b	c	Last two digits from prev. Hash	Hash	Divid 3
2											
3	1	Red	ad59dn	25		82	65	25	12	160	

Hash = Nonce+a+b+c – Value of Last 2 digits of Prev Hash

Blockwaste example, step 6: find Nonce

1	Block	Area	Householder	Total waste	Nonce (1-3)	a	b	c	Last two digits from prev. Hash	Hash	Divid 3
2											
3	1	Red	ad59dn	2	2	82	65	25	12	217	

Hash = Nonce+a+b+c – Value of Last 2 digits of Prev Hash

Used materials

- [SuperDataScience](https://www.superdatascience.com/pages/blockchain) course for Blockchain, <https://www.superdatascience.com/pages/blockchain>
- [Telmo Subira Rodriguez](https://medium.com/swlh/blockchain-for-dummies-d3daf2170068), Blockchain for Dummies, <https://medium.com/swlh/blockchain-for-dummies-d3daf2170068>
- **Blockwaste project materials**, <https://blockwasteproject.eu/>

Blockwaste Game

Introduction to the game

- Interactive role-playing game focused on MSW management
- Two roles: the 'Mayor' and the 'households'
- An iterative process of 12 steps (i.e. months)
- An online app accompanied with an Excel file demonstrating all the calculations behind the tool

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The roles of the game

A. Households - Input

- Household members
- MSW generation per capita and year
- Composition of household's MSW
- Time spent on sorting waste (in minutes per week) – it defines the segregation and recycling rate

The screenshot displays the input interface for households in the BC4 ECO app. It includes the following elements:

- Add data** button
- Household members ***: 4
- MSW generation ***: 420 pc/year
- Waste Composition Sliders**:
 - Organic: 39%
 - Paper: 24%
 - Plastic: 20%
 - Metal: 4%
 - Glass: 4%
 - Other: 9%
- Time spent on sorting waste (between 0-45) ***: 25 minutes per week
- Choose month ***: March

25

The roles of the game

A. Households - Results

- Municipal fees
- MSW management decisions and municipal fees for other households (non-sensitive info)

Household	MH members	MBTF generation per year	MH MBTF generation/ month	Time spent on sorting waste (between 0-45 minutes per week)	Value of time (Euro/ hour month)	Percentage of recyclables separated (different bins)	percentage of mixed MBTF (mixed waste, organic and other)	Total cost (Euro/month)	Municipal fees (Euro/month)
January									
Me	2	410	68.33	35	15	100%	0%	21.5	6.5
PK2	N/A	N/A	34.17	N/A	N/A	75%	25%	N/A	4
February									
Me	2	410	68.33	40	15	100%	0%	21	6
PK2	N/A	N/A	34.17	N/A	N/A	75%	25%	N/A	6
Total				75	€30.00			€42.50	€12.50

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The roles of the game

B. Mayor – Initial input

- S1. Aerobic MBTF (mixed waste) – Aerobic BTF for separated organics and MRF for separated recyclables
- S2. Anaerobic MBTF (mixed waste) – Aerobic BTF for separated organics and MRF for separated recyclables
- S3. Anaerobic MBTF (mixed waste) – Anaerobic BTF for separated organics and MRF for separated recyclables
- S4. Biodrying MBTF (mixed waste) - Anaerobic BTF for separated organics and MRF for separated recyclables

Choose your plan

As the mayor, you have to select a plan for ...

Choose wisely!

S1. Aerobic MBT - Compost

S2. Anaerobic MBT - Compost

S3. Anaerobic MBT - Anaerobic

S4. Biodrying MBT - Anaerobic

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The roles of the game

B. Mayor – Main input

- Municipal fees per household based on:
 - Mixed, separated and total waste generated by each household and
 - ‘Net cost’ for the Municipality per household knowing the total Net cost for mixed waste per kg (€/kg), the total Net cost for separated waste per kg (€/kg) and the total Net cost for mixed waste per kg (€/kg)

Balance: -€11.31

Month: All Household: All

Household	Mixed collected waste (kg)	Separated collected waste (kg)	Total waste collected (kg)	Net cost for municipality	Municipal fees (Euro/month)	
January						
PK1	0	68.33	68.33	€6.63	Fee €6.63	Save
PK2	8.543	25.628	34.17	€3.34	Fee €4.00	Save
February						
PK1	0	68.33	68.33	€6.63	Fee €6.63	Save
PK2	8.543	25.628	34.17	€3.34	Fee €6.63	Save
March						
PK1	35	105	140	€13.85	Fee €	Save
Total	52.085	292.515	345	€33.81	€22.90	

The only rule that should be followed is that the “Balance” for the Municipality cannot be negative

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The roles of the game

B. Mayor – Results

- Further financial details
- Material flows

Month: All Household: All Plan: S1_Aerobic_MBT - Com. Show MBT, Biowaste, and MRF data

Month	Collection cost		Treatment cost		Landfill cost		Total cost		Revenues		Net cost		Net cost / waste (kg)			
	Mixed	Separated	Mixed	Separated	cost	Mixed	Separated	Total	Mixed	Separated	Total	Mixed	Separated	Total		
January	€0.5	€11.6	€0.6	€5.3	€0.2	€1.3	€17.0	€18.3	€0.5	€7.8	€3.3	€9.1	€10.0	0.1	0.097	
February	€0.5	€11.6	€0.6	€5.3	€0.2	€1.3	€17.0	€18.3	€0.5	€7.8	€3.3	€9.1	€10.0	0.1	0.097	
March	€2.1	€14.0	€2.5	€5.9	€0.9	€5.4	€19.8	€25.3	€2.0	€9.5	€11.4	€3.5	€10.4	€13.9	0.1	0.099
April	€0.0	€0.0	€0.0	€0.0	€0.0	€0.0	€0.0	€0.0	€0.0	€0.0	€0.0	€0.0	€0.0	0	0	
May	€0.0	€0.0	€0.0	€0.0	€0.0	€0.0	€0.0	€0.0	€0.0	€0.0	€0.0	€0.0	€0.0	0	0	

Link to the game:
<https://game.blockwasteproject.eu/home>

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At the end of the game...

Let's discuss:

- What were the players' concerns as regards their roles?
- Did they change their strategy as the game progressed based on the results they received?
- Were they affected by what other 'households' did?
- What was the most important issue for them towards selecting a specific strategy (e.g. maximisation of environmental benefits, minimisation of cost, etc.)?

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Thank you!

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Appendix 2: Copenhagen Summer School - Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

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ECO**

**Copenhagen – Summer
School**

Copenhagen.
25 April 2023

Sustainable Development Goals
(SDGs)
Slides provided by Prof. Istemi Demirag.
Taltech

TAL TECH UNIVERSITY OF LIMERICK OLLSCOIL LIMERIGH GALSWORTHY UNIVERSITY

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What is and why Sustainable Development ?

**“Development that meets the needs of the present
without compromising the ability of future generations
to meet their own needs”**

*(the globally accepted definition adopted in 1987 at the
World Commission on Environment and Development)*

Sustainable Development Goals therefore the criteria for achieving social, political and economic progress in ways that will not exhaust the earth's finite resources and not exploit or impoverish one grouping of people for the enrichment of another.

2

What are the Dimensions of Sustainable Development?

3

Time Dimensions of Sustainable Development

What are the 2030 Sustainable Development Goals?

After three years of debate and negotiations, on September 25, 2015, all 193 member nations of the United Nations, including the United States, unanimously voted to adopt the global Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), which declare:

“On behalf of the peoples we serve, we have adopted a historic decision on a comprehensive, far-reaching and people-centered set of universal and transformative goals and targets. We commit ourselves to working tirelessly for the full implementation of this agenda by 2030.”

Declaration of the 2030 Agenda for sustainable Development

Source: <https://sdgs.un.org/2030agenda>

Source: <https://sdgs.un.org/goals>

6

How are the SDGs supposed to be implemented?

- “...all member states to develop as soon as practicable, ambitious national responses to the overall implementation of this Agenda. These can...build on existing planning instruments, such as national development and sustainable development strategies, as appropriate.”
- “...the essential role of national parliaments through their enactment of legislation and adoption of budgets and their role in ensuring accountability for the effective implementation of our commitments.”
- “...governments and public institutions...work closely on implementation with regional and local authorities, sub-regional institutions, international institutions, academia, philanthropic organizations, volunteer groups and others.”

Source: <https://sdgs.un.org/2030agenda>

7

From the Brundtland report to the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development

8

Global monitoring – Main actors

9

Thank you!

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Appendix 3: Copenhagen Summer School - Intro to DLTs

Copenhagen – Summer school

Copenhagen,
25 April 2023

Intro to DLTs

Sadok Ben Yahia
Tiziana Margaria
Salim Saay

BC4ECO has received funding from the Erasmus+ cooperation partnerships in higher education, under grant Agreement No KA220-HED-2021-003

Introduction

- DLT (Distributed Ledger Technology) decentralises data storage and processing, has different types:
- Blockchain: Chain of blocks with transactions linked through consensus, such as Bitcoin, Ethereum
- Hashgraph: Gossip protocol combined with voting for consensus.
- DLT applied in:
- Financial Sector such as Cryptocurrencies, Smart Contracts, Supply Chain Management,
- Healthcare, Secure Patient Records
- Voting Systems, Transparent and Tamper-Proof

Introduction to Blockchain

3

Basic concepts

4

What is Blockchain?

- A blockchain is a decentralized database encompassing a physical chain of blocks of fixed length.
- Each block comprises 1 or more transactions
- Transactions are added to a new block to be validated and then inserted into the block.
- When the block is validated, it is added to the end of the existing blockchain.
- Only two operations (unlike classic CRUD) are adding a transaction and displaying a transaction,

5

Blockchain

*A Blockchain is a **replicated** database, managed by a **consensus** mechanism, in a **peer-to-peer** network of **non-trusting** parties*

- Blockchain can be simply defined as a **time-stamped** series of data **records** that are managed by a cluster of **nodes**.
- Nodes are computers that are connected in a peer-to-peer network and have an identical copy of the data.
- A new data entry is validated and transmitted to the entire network to maintain the identical copy of the database.

6

What is Blockchain?

- A Blockchain manages a doubly linked list of ordered blocks
 - Each block
 - has average size of 1MB
 - contains control data of around 200 bytes, such as timestamp, link to the previous block, other fields

<https://www.blockchain.com/charts/avg-block-size>

7

Block concept

- A blockchain is a distributed ledger of transactions.
 - Transactions are implemented as data grouped into blocks.
 - Transactions use cryptographic validation to link blocks together.
 - Each block references and identifies the previous block using a hash function that forms an unbroken chain (i.e., a chain of blocks).

8

Structure of a blockchain

- Once saved, the blocks are designed to **resist any modification**
 - Block data cannot be changed **retroactively**.
- New data is added
 - To the old ones, i.e., data is **only written, never deleted**.
 - In **batches** or in **blocks** and then added to existing **blocks**, forming a **blockchain**.
- Not only does everyone have the same database (blockchain), but everyone has a copy of the blockchain that only they can access.

9

Distributed Ledger

- A blockchain is run autonomously through a distributed peer-to-peer (Peer2Peer) network of independent parties.
- Blockchains are considered as
 - Open and distributed ledgers (ledger or Ledger) that
 - Can record transactions in an efficient, verifiable, and permanent way.
 - The ledger itself can also be programmed to trigger transactions automatically.

10

10

Public Blockchain

- The public blockchain does not have a central authority to manage usernames and passwords, so it uses cryptography.
- While anyone can see the data tagged with your address in the blockchain, no one is allowed to change it.
- It can only be changed by the person who can prove they are the owner via the private key.

11

11

Public, private, and consortium blockchains

Blockchains can be classified into public, private, and consortium blockchain based on their settings.

A **Public Blockchain** is permissionless if the platform is publicly open for users without permission from any authority.

Generally, in a public blockchain all transactions are visible to the public.

Bitcoin is a well-known example of a public blockchain.

A **Private Blockchain** is not entirely open for the public to use:

a centralized authority controls and defines who has the right to join the network.

Thus a private blockchain is considered to be centralized due to the fact that a single authority maintains the network.

Besides, data in a private blockchain is prone to tampering.

Examples of private blockchain: Corda, Hyperledger Fabric, and Hyperledger Sawtooth.

12

12

Public, private, and consortium blockchains

A **Consortium Blockchain** has different organizations involved to manage a shared blockchain.

The authority is distributed among different organizations, thus the consortium blockchain is considered to have *semi-decentralized* management and governance.

In a consortium blockchain,

- only a preselected set of nodes participates in the consensus process.
- a limited number of trusted participants are required to validate the block.

This is what makes the consortium blockchain highly scalable and guarantees high throughput.

A consortium blockchain is best suitable for organizational collaboration.

13

Blockchain as a data structure

- The blockchain **data structure** consists of a **chain of blocks**.
- Each block records **transactions** validated in a particular period that have not yet been recorded in any prior blocks.
- These blocks are linked to one another through a **cryptographic hash** such that each subsequent block contains the hash of the previous block (also called parent) header and hence constitutes a chain.
- The first block, known as the **genesis block**, has no reference to a previous block since it has no parent block.
- This **linkability** is a cryptographic mechanism that maintains data integrity and immutability in the network.

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Addresses in the blockchain

- What is also amazing in this system is that anyone can generate an address on their own, in isolation, without worrying that they will run into someone else's address.
- The reason is that there are so many possible addresses that it's essentially impossible to bump into another address, even if you tried.
- <https://www.blockchain.com/fr/explorer>

15

15

Summarizing the notion of the Blockchain

- Blockchain is a distributed, transparent, immutable, validated, secure and pseudo-anonymous database that exists as multiple nodes, so if 51% of the nodes agree, trust in the chain is guaranteed.
 - The blockchain is distributed because a complete copy resides on as many nodes as in the system.
 - The blockchain is immutable because none of the transactions can be modified.
 - The blockchain is validated (for example in the Bitcoin space) by the miners compensated for the construction of the next secure block.
 - The blockchain is pseudo-anonymous because the identity of the people involved in the transaction is represented by an address key in the form of a random string.

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The transactions

- Transactions are signed messages generated by an external account, transmitted by the network, and recorded on the blockchain.
- The structure of a transaction:
 - **Nonce**: Sequence number, issued by the originating EOA, used to prevent a replay of the message.
 - **Gas price**: The gas price (in wei) that the initiator is willing to pay
 - **Gas limit**: The maximum amount of gas the initiator is willing to buy for this trade
 - **Recipient**: The destination Ethereum address
 - **Value**: The amount of ether to send to the destination
 - **Data**: The variable-length binary data payload
 - **V, r, s**: The three components of an originating EOA ECDSA digital signature
- Unit of record: smallest piece of information application-related information that is stored in the chain as a transaction.

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Nonce concept

- The Nonce is one of the most important components.
- Nonce is:
 - **scalar value** equal to the number of transactions sent from this address
 - or, in the case of accounts with an associated code, the number of contract creations made by this account.
 - It is calculated dynamically, by counting the number of confirmed transactions from an address.

In general - In finance and cryptography, a nonce refers to a randomly generated number, and it is used to verify transactions or perform security checks. For example, the captchas we often find on websites are nonces (albeit with letters included) as they are used just once

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The transactions: terminology

EOA: Externally Owned Account (EOA)

ECDSA signatures: Elliptic Curve Distributed Signature Algorithms

V: Value A scalar value equal to the number of Wei to be transferred to the message call's recipient or, in the case of contract creation, as an endowment to the newly created account

r, s: Values corresponding to the signature of the transaction and used to determine the sender of the transaction

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How does this all relate to blockchain?

- Blockchains are completely decentralized registers, without any central control authority.
 - How can the network be sure that the transaction is valid?
 - If someone doesn't try to spend the same money twice.
- A BFT-type consensus algorithm is essential.
 - Bitcoin implements a probabilistic variant of consensus, **Proof-of-Work**
 - Ethereum implements another consensus variant, **Proof-of-Stake**

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Example of blockchain miners

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Power & Trust in the Blockchain

With its transparency, immutability and decentralization, blockchain-based systems are able represent and manage power and trust better

- **Power/trust mechanisms:** processes that are used to establish trust (e.g. cryptography, consensus algorithms)
- **Moments of trust:** point in time when a participant in a blockchain network must place trust in another participant
- **Trust loop:** iterative process of building trust within a blockchain network by continuing participation and good behaviour.
- **Provenance:** origin or history of a particular unit record on the blockchain.

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Ethereum as an example chain

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Ethereum: data structure

The **block's header** comprises metadata,
Its **body** comprises multiple types of data, namely:

- transactions,
- receipts, and
- system states (account states).

Each of these data types is organized into a Merkle tree or a Patricia tree (Radix tree) in the state tree.

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Ethereum costs

To prevent Denial-of-Service (DoS) attack, EVM adopts the gas system: every computation of a program must be paid for upfront in a dedicated unit called **gas** as defined by the protocol.

If the provided amount of gas does not cover the cost of execution, the transaction fails.

The block size is controlled by the **gas-limit**, which the miners (i.e. producers of new blocks) define, and a constant rise of the gas-limit happens.

In decentralized systems like Ethereum, we need to ensure that everyone agrees on the order of transactions. Miners help this happen by **solving computationally difficult puzzles to produce blocks, securing the network from attacks.**

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Cryptography

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Introduction to Crypto

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Cryptography in the blockchain

- Cryptography is a branch of mathematics widely used in computer security.
- Cryptography can also be used
 - to prove knowledge of a secret without revealing that secret (a digital signature),
 - Or to prove the authenticity of data (with fingerprints, also called “hashes”).
- These types of cryptographic proofs are essential mathematical tools for the operation of all blockchain systems.

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Asymmetric Cryptography

- It is an encryption method that uses two keys (a public key and a private key) that are **mathematically** similar but not identical
 - It uses an advanced category of mathematical functions called elliptic curves
 - It is impossible to guess the private key from the public key
 - Therefore, public keys can be shared safely
- The blockchain system uses asymmetric cryptography to create the public key and the private key

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Public key and private key

- In an asymmetric cryptosystem, keys exist in pairs:
 - A public key for encryption;
 - A secret key (private key) for decryption.
- When a user wishes to send a message to another user,
 - he only needs to encrypt the message to be sent using the public key of the recipient
 - Demo: <https://github.com/hakiri/public-private-key-demo>

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Hash functions

- A hash function is any function that can be used to map data of arbitrary size to data of fixed size.
 - The input to a hash function is called a pre-image, the message, or simply the input data.
 - The output is called the hash.
- Hash functions are used to transform public keys into account addresses in the blockchain, e.g., Ethereum.
- They can also be used to create fingerprints to facilitate data verification.

Digital signatures

- Digital signatures can be used to present proof of ownership of a private key without revealing that private key.
- It is based on the Elliptic Curve Digital Signature Algorithm (ECDSA), which is itself based on elliptic curve private-public key pairs.
- A digital signature performs three functions
 - First, the signature proves that the owner of the private key, who implicitly owns an Ethereum account, authorized the spending of ether or the performance of a contract.
 - Second, it guarantees non-repudiation: the proof of authorization is undeniable.
 - Third, the signature proves that the transaction data has not been and cannot be modified by anyone after the transaction was signed.

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How do digital signatures work?

- A digital signature is a mathematical scheme consisting of two parts.
 - The first part is an algorithm to **create a signature**, using a **private key** (the signing key), **from a message** (which in our case is the transaction).
 - The second part is an algorithm that allows anyone to **verify the signature** using only the **message** and a **public key**.

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Thank you!

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Appendix 4: Design Brief

Module 1 - Workshop Activities Design Brief

The River **Blue** is an excellent resource for the city of **Louisville**. It provides drinking water for its inhabitants while sustaining a diverse ecosystem of aquatic plants, animals, and microorganisms. During the summer, the river is also used for recreational activities and becomes an essential resource for local farmers who irrigate their crops. Following governmental regulations, a wastewater treatment plant collects and treats the wastewater from the city's municipal sewerage to cope with the city's ongoing industrialisation. Together with other industrial facilities, they influence the river's water quality. Local communities of volunteers organise themselves to collectively clean the river's banks from plastic and unsorted floating waste.

The city's recent development has led many industries, such as power plants and manufacturing industries, to use the river water for their cooling processes, textile production & finishing. Besides using the water for irrigation, the farmers employ it to clean fresh products (vegetables, fruits) before supplying the local markets. To worsen the situation, the pressure on agricultural production has led many farmers to use fertilisers and pesticides on their crops, carried by rain and irrigation to the nearby streams, further polluting the water. The intense and unregulated use of resources and rising concerns related to seasonal droughts deteriorated the water quality. They reduced many recreation opportunities, posing a significant threat to the ecosystem's health by making the water unsuitable for human consumption.

Stakeholders:

Farmers in the surrounding areas use the river by drawing its water for irrigation. When some started adopting pesticides and fertilisers for their crops, many of those chemicals eventually ran off and contaminated the river's waters.

They contribute to the city's industrialisation, including manufacturers employing water for cooling processes on heavy machinery, textile production, and food suppliers that provide fresh produce to local markets. Besides contributing to withdrawing water resources from the river, some industries discharge untreated waste into the river, leading to further contamination. They lack clear incentives and regulations on how to manage the river's resources.

They should monitor and regulate water quality and ensure compliance with the established regulations and policies. The government interacts with industries, farmers, and local communities to explore new solutions and reduce the consequences of poor water quality management.

Besides being the primary users of the river's water resources, they might also organise local groups often involved in activities to clean up the river and raise awareness about the importance of maintaining a healthy ecosystem.

The local wastewater treatment plant is a facility that treats wastewater from various sources, such as residential, commercial, and industrial sources, to remove contaminants and pollutants (organic matter, nutrients and metals) before it is discharged back into the river. They follow governmental regulations and collaborate with the city's ecosystem.

Aquatic plants, animals, and microorganisms, play a critical role in the ecosystem for water management. They are directly affected by the consequences of water quality while also trying to contribute by helping to maintain the balance of nutrients, oxygen levels, and waste removal. For example, aquatic plants help to absorb excess nutrients and chemicals, while microorganisms break down organic matter, converting it into nutrients that can be reused by other organisms.

Key considerations:

Overall, **Distributed Ledger Technologies** have the potential to create more *transparency*, *accountability*, and *efficiency* in the management of water resources and contribute to

enhancing the water quality, making it more accessible to everyone while rebalancing the ecosystem. Be critical of adopting such technology within the brief, and try to challenge your biases and assumptions on the topic.

We've listed several questions which can be relevant to - and not limited to this case:

- How might we create more transparent and efficient mechanisms for water allocation among industries that draw from the river banks to incentivise industries to adopt more sustainable water management?
- How might we monitor and track the discharge of pollutants into the river and incentivise sustainable practices among industries and farmers?
- How can we hold industries accountable for the unregulated misuse of the river banks while integrating strategies for regulation and non-compliance measures?
- How might we ensure rewards to those players in the ecosystem that encourage or work towards the adoption of more sustainable practices for water usage?
- How might DLT technologies create more sustainable and autonomous ecosystems incentivised by decentralised and transparent ways of doing?

GOOD TO KNOW:

The brief you have been presented is fictional. You are welcome to use it as it is or integrate it with other perspectives if you find it relevant. F.e., we listed several stakeholders interacting with the ecosystem, but you are welcome to challenge them and create new ones if necessary. This brief only provides you with an initial challenge and some guiding questions on how to address it; nevertheless, we welcome groups to challenge the brief and take different directions if they are more comfortable.

The goal is to become familiar with novel technologies, environmental issues, and different and innovative ways of tackling challenges and working together. We will not evaluate your ideas based on their accuracy, but we will evaluate your critical thinking process and how you work together in groups.

Appendix 5: Copenhagen Summer School - DLTs and Blockchain examples / A

The slide features a blue-to-green gradient background. In the top left corner, the BC4 ECO logo is displayed in white. The main title 'Copenhagen – Summer school' is positioned on the left, with the date 'Copenhagen, 25 April 2023' below it. On the right, the subtitle 'DLTs and Blockchain examples' is underlined, followed by the names of the presenters: Sadok Ben Yahia, Salim Saay, and Tiziana Margaria. The bottom of the slide contains logos for TAL TECH, UNIVERSITY OF LIMERICK, and UNIVERSITY OF LONDON, along with a text box stating that BC4ECO received funding from the Erasmus+ program and the European Union flag.

**BC4
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Copenhagen – Summer school

Copenhagen,
25 April 2023

DLTs and Blockchain examples

Sadok Ben Yahia
Salim Saay
Tiziana Margaria

TAL TECH

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Examples of Blockchain Use

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Blockchain Use Cases

- The hottest Blockchain technology use cases are categorized under specific industries/applications:
 - Decentralized computing & Smart Contracts.
 - Internet of Things (IoT)
 - Banking & Money Transfer (FinTech).
 - Cryptocurrency
 - Non-fungible token (NFT)
 - Identity Management & Security. (SSI)
 - Logistics & Supply chains.
 - Digital Media. ...
 - Governments & Education
 - Healthcare & Medical Field

Blockchain's Use Cases

Blockchain is so much more than Bitcoin, NFTs, & Crypto!

3

Blockchain Application Areas

- Professional use cases
 - Cryptocurrency and Digital Tokens
 - Banking and financial services
- Technology use cases
 - Distributed storage systems
 - Distributed computing
 - Decentralized communications
- Legal and governance use cases
 - The Beginning of Autonomous Law: A Smart Contract
 - Decentralized autonomous organizations

Enterprise blockchain solutions development

<https://openledger.info/solutions/>

Cryptocurrency

- More than 9000 cryptocurrencies have been introduced
- New cryptocurrencies appear every day and others disappear
 - Bitcoin (BTC)
 - Ethereum (ETH)
 - Ripple (XRP)
 - Bitcoin Cash (BCH)
 - Stellar Lumens (XLM)
 - EOS (EOS)
 - Litecoin (LTC)
 - Cardano (ADA)
- Bitcoin was built with a limited supply of 21 million coins.
 - Coins are gradually introduced to the market through a complex process, which is called "mining".
 - Mining is the essential process of validation, verification, and commitment,
 - In 2018, 80% bitcoin stock was introduced (over 10 years)

<https://coinmarketcap.com>

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Digital Tokens

- A digital token can be any type of digital asset or any digital representation of a physical asset.
- In Ethereum, a digital token can represent any fungible and tradable commodity, such as
 - Currency,
 - Loyalty points: a points-based loyalty program that rewards customers for specific behaviors
 - gift certificates, gift cards, etc.

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Digital Tokens

- Ethereum tokens use ERC20 token
- Their importance has increased significantly with venture capital investments and institutional investors
 - Initial Coin Offering (ICO), a form of crowdfunding
 - Raise funds by creating and selling their own digital tokens through crowdfunding.
 - Tokens can be converted into any currency at the current market rate.

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Know Your Customer (KYC) in banking

- KYC means Know Your Customer and sometimes Know Your Client.
- KYC check is the mandatory process of identifying and verifying the client's identity when opening an account and periodically over time.
- In other words, banks must make sure that their clients are genuinely who they claim to be.
- Banks may refuse to open an account or halt a business relationship if the client fails to meet minimum KYC requirements.

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Traditional banking vs KYC banking

- Fight against financial crime and money laundering, and customer identification
- ensure customer compliance with anti-corruption legislation
- check their probity and integrity
- prevent identity theft, tax evasion, money laundering, and terrorism financing
- These processes are typically done by:
 - data collection and analysis, behavior and transaction analysis, etc.
 - verification of the presence on blacklists,

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Blockchain for Fintech

- Decentralized Finance is the evolution that utilizes decentralized smart contracts.
 - reduces the risks associated,
 - speeds up the settlement process,
 - enhances trade accuracy
 - blockchain's potential for immutability is helping with lowering the possibility of errors
 - ensuring the integrity of records for financial reporting and audits
 - Blockchain can help with a digital identity system
 - Manage identity data
 - Share data with others minus safety risks
 - Digitally sign documents like claims and transactions.
 - New crowdfunding models

Primary benefits of blockchain according to Fis Exploring or using the tech

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Governance 2.0

Blockchain Is Helping to Build a New Kind of Energy Grid

Using the technology behind Bitcoin, participants in the Brooklyn Microgrid are buying and selling locally generated renewable energy over a peer-to-peer network.

April 19, 2017

How Blockchain Can Bring Financial Services to the Poor

A project from the Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation aims to use distributed ledger technology to help the two billion people worldwide who lack bank accounts.

April 18, 2017

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Asset Management Regulations: issues

- Traditional Assets management in the back office can be tedious, risky, and time-consuming.
 - This is especially the case when manual steps are involved, such as during matching and reconciliation tasks.
- Each entity in the value chain maintains its own copy, or view, of the transactions that have taken place.
- These processes continue to become more complicated as new instruments are developed and marketed.
- Errors and the associated costs increase in proportion to the complexity of the tasks and the involvement of resources to process them.

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Asset Management Regulations: solution

- Transactions can be stored in a blockchain and made available to all parties.
- Radically simplify and streamline this whole process for all parties.
- Automate the trading lifecycle, facilitate data management, and provide transparency as well as a substantial reduction in infrastructure and resources.
- These improvements allow for minimal reconciliation and ultimately faster processing times.
- Although all transactions can be visible to everyone, it is possible to organize and configure them in such a way that only certain parties are aware of this information.

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Insurance Claims Processing

1. The customer submits his complaint to the Smart Contract
2. Assessor reviews and approves the application
3. An insurance company approves the claim and funds the repair
4. The customer chooses a repair shop
5. Repairs made
6. The customer accepts the repaired car
7. Payment for repairs

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Pharmaceutical supply chain

Traditional model

Blockchain model

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Transfer of automobile ownership

- Self-driving cars use a consensus algorithm to trade ownership between different buyers
- PoO: Proof-of-Ownership
- Example:
 - Cube ICO - Blockchain Security for Tesla Cars <https://cubeint.io/>

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Decentralized Autonomous Organizations (DAO)

- Distributed Collaborative Organizations
 - Integration of blockchain-based distributed organizations (DAOs) with the existing legal system
- DAO is an emerging form of legal structure that has no central governing body
 - members share a common goal to act in the best interest of the entity
 - The organization uses rules coded as smart contracts
 - The financial transaction record and program rules of a DAO are kept in a blockchain.
 - The concept introduces several models described in a "white paper"

<https://github.com/the-dao/whitepaper>

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Decentralized Autonomous Organizations (DAO)

- DAO (Slock.it, 2016)
 - the DAO raises the equivalent of \$150m to invest in startups
 - 14% of all ether ever issued on Ethereum
 - Largest crowdfunding project of all times
 - **A DAO can cross jurisdictional boundaries**
 - the nodes of a blockchain can be in any country in the world.

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Distributed File System (IPFS)

- Swarm
 - is a distributed storage platform and content distribution service
 - A native base layer service of the Ethereum web3 stack
 - Provide a decentralized and redundant store for DApp code, user data, blockchain, and state data.

<https://ethersphere.github.io/swarm-home/>

Distributed File System (IPFS)

- Storj Storage Nodes
 - It uses encryption, file sharing, and a blockchain-based hash table to store files on a peer-to-peer network.
 - The goal is to make cloud file storage faster, cheaper, and more private.

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Distributed File System (IPFS)

- INFURA
 - high availability of blockchain APIs and developer tools
 - High availability API connects applications of all sizes to decentralized and scalable storage on IPFS
 - Content will always be pinned, immutable, and instantly available, even when you go offline.
 - <https://www.infura.io/>

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Thank you!

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Appendix 6: Copenhagen Summer School - DLTs and Blockchain examples / B

The slide features a blue-to-green gradient background. In the top left corner, the 'BC4 ECO' logo is displayed in a white, digital-style font. The main title 'Copenhagen – Summer school' is positioned on the left side, with the date '25 April 2023' below it. On the right side, the subtitle 'DLTs and Blockchain examples' is underlined, followed by the names of the presenters: Sadok Ben Yahia, Salim Saay, and Tiziana Margaria. The bottom of the slide contains several logos: 'TAL TECH' in pink, the 'UNIVERSITY OF LIMERICK' logo, the 'UNIVERSITY OF ALABAMA' logo, and the European Union flag. A small text block on the right side of the bottom section states: 'BC4ECO has received funding from the Erasmus+ cooperation partnerships in higher education, under grant Agreement No KA220-HED-2021-003'.

**BC4
ECO**

Copenhagen – Summer school

Copenhagen.
25 April 2023

DLTs and Blockchain examples

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Blockchain Case Study

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Introduction

- **TISVChain**, a framework based on blockchain to handle the issues of counterfeit vaccine and vaccine supply chain problems like transparency, immutability, and traceability
- public blockchain: Ethereum, smart contracts (Solidity language), very low gas cost
- Improves security: offline unique account addresses in blockchain-based frameworks
- improves overall efficiency of the framework
 - keeping the gas cost low,
 - decrease the number of lost blocks □ keep low propagation delay,
 - high TPS value (transactions per second)

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Fake vaccines are a serious problem

In traditional vaccine supply chains, the government's supervision departments have monitored the entire vaccine journey.

A successful and safe vaccine supply chain requires an effective and traceable logistics system of the **end-to-end supply chain**.

World Health Organization:

- thousands of deaths occur in developing countries due to fake drugs
- around 30% of the total medicine sold in Latin America, Africa, and Asia are counterfeit.

In Pakistan, around 40-50% of drugs are fake

Estimated annual business loss of US pharmaceutical industries due to counterfeiting: \$200 billion USD

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Supply Chain management problem

Drugs are moved across different complex distributed networks:

- difficult to detect counterfeiting,
- creates opportunities for fake drugs to enter the authentic supply chain.

Successful initiatives against such practices, like the IDMP standards in the European Union, but this is not the practice at a global scale.

IDMP is a suite of five standards developed within the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) to facilitate the unique **identification of medicinal products** in the context of pharmacovigilance and the safety of medications throughout the world.

- **immutable, well-maintained supply chains**

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Traditional drugs Supply Chain

High drug research costs upfront

- Lack of **transparency**: visibility of the vaccine supply chain
- Lack of **traceability**: an own database at each step, manual record of each product

Smart contracts, blockchain-managed supply chain

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Traditional drugs Supply Chain

- **Trust issue**: maintaining trust in a complex supply chain
- **Cold-chain shipping**: guarantee appropriate refrigeration at every step
- **Fake drugs**: outdated information sharing, breaches allow entries and exits, i.e. counterfeits
- **Single point of failure**: current centralized cloud systems are vulnerable; each individual has little control over the (own) data as the cloud provider is a 3rd party.

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Traditional drugs Supply Chain

- Unreliable reputation systems:** feedback goes to the end point, or a third party (if managed in the cloud) with risk of information losses and tampering
 immutable and transparent reputation system
- Contracts and documentation:** paperwork for different transactions, change of ownership, a letter of credit – outdated and complicated
 Smart contracts system: automate the transactions, immutable records

Vaccine Supply Chain

What: Real product
How: Cold box, refrigerators, cold rooms, freezers

- Integrity
- Confidentiality
- Availability
- Traceability
- Auditability

At every step
 and every hand-over

TISVChain

Transparent Immutable Secure Vaccine Supply Chain

- design a decentralized vaccine supply chain data management system using blockchain technology
- ensure authenticity, immutability, and traceability of supply chain data
- compute/examine the performance of the framework by different performance metrics
- deployable on both
 - private (Geth PoA visual studio code)
 - public blockchain (Ethereum, remix IDE, solidity)

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Registering a Manufacturer

If a **vaccine manufacturer (VM)** wants to **produce** a vaccine it must **get approval** from **regulatory authority (RA)**

Once approval is given for the specific vaccine, the **VM** is **licensed** to produce only that specific vaccine.

If RA approves the VM for the production of a vaccine, then the RA will assign to the VM a **unique offline account address (UA)** in the form of a **160-bit identifier**.

This is additional security: only manufacturers with a UA will be allowed to produce vaccines.

To get access to the blockchain framework, the VM will put his **UA on the blockchain**.

After that, the VM will decide which **distributor** can **distribute** the vaccine.

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Approving a Batch

When the VM has produced a vaccine batch, **ready for delivery**, the RA checks that it meets the **standard requirements**.

If the vaccine meets the standard, the RA **approves** it for distribution:

- RA enters its **standard rating** (from 1 to 5) in the blockchain, and
- it gets **dispatched** for distribution.

At every node the transaction information is stored on the blockchain.

At every node, the terms of agreement are stated as a **smart contract**.

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Vaccine Distribution

The VMs enter the information of the **authorized distributors** in the blockchain. Only those distributors will be able to distribute.

A **distributor** further dispatches the vaccine to the **wholesalers**.

The wholesalers dispatch it to **pharmacies** and **hospitals**.

Finally, the vaccine is received by the **patient** or consumer.

The pharmacy/hospital can **verify** the data of the vaccine by scanning the **barcode**.

They can also verify the **integrity of the vaccine in the blockchain**: at every node, the transaction is stored on the blockchain.

This ensures the immutability and integrity of the vaccine data at any time.

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Smart contracts and verification

In a traditional SC, the pharmacy/hospital can **verify** the data of the vaccine by scanning the **barcode**.

It mostly contains the product name and some additional data.

Now they can also verify the **integrity of the vaccine in the blockchain**: at every node, that transaction is stored on the blockchain.

This ensures the immutability and integrity of the vaccine data at any time.

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TISVChain system model

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TISVChain Logic

- 1. Publish Smart Contract:** The RA publishes its smart contract over a blockchain platform. The smart contract contains the information on which kind of company is allowed to manufacture vaccines, information about vaccine registration, and decides about the vaccine approval when a vaccine meets certain quality standards.
- 2. Data Store:** Once the smart contracts are published by the RA all the information is stored on the blockchain as it is a peer-to-peer network, so its copy is shared to all connected nodes.
- 3. Request for Registration:** The VM company requests the RA to register the company so they can start producing the vaccine.
- 4. Offline Unique Account Address:** when a company requests RA approval, the RA rates the company's production quality standard on a scale 1 to 10. If the rating is equal or over 5 points, the RA assigns that company an offline 160-bit unique account number (UA).

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TISVChain Logic

5. **Update data accordingly:** The RA updates the data. Once a UA is assigned to a company, it updates the smart contract on the blockchain accordingly.
6. **Access through the UA:** A company can access the smart contracts on the blockchain only if it has a valid UA. Only then a company is considered as a registered company, and can put its required data on the blockchain network.
7. **Authorized distributors and wholesalers:** Registered VMs companies decide which distributors and wholesalers are authorized to deal with its vaccine. Only those distributors and wholesalers are allowed to work, as they are authorized by the VM company.
8. **Hospitals and pharmacies:** Authorized distributors will deliver the vaccine to hospitals and pharmacies, where consumers can receive it.
9. **Patients/consumers:** Even the patients and consumers would be able to get the information about the vaccine in transparent, immutable, and secure form just by scanning a barcode.

Implementation on Ethereum

VM interaction with smart contracts

Consumer interaction w. smart contracts

Algorithms

Algorithm 1: GetRegCompany	
Step 1	: if (_standard_rating_score>5) Transaction Hash (0xd249bf3e60ebd312acf41f8de5602efb1215841278d2fcc6e428ab02558366ac)
Step 2	: Assign Unique account address (0x5B38Da6a701c568545dCfE875f56beddC4)
Step 3	: else String memory temp_standard_remark= "low standard rating improve quality"
Step 4	: End
Algorithm 2: Verify unique account address (0x5B38Da6a701c568545dCfE875f56beddC4) (from) (0xd9145CCCE52D386f254917e481eB44e9943F39138) (to Regulatory authority)	
Step 1	: emit LogApproved(Msg.sender, Unique_address) Transaction Hash 0x273d5cc12a1f54624405f94c5bb73cb5fe6669197942cde5d1ab8ca2208323e
Step 2	: if Approved_address [unique_address] = true
Step 3	: else return false
Step 4	: End

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Algorithms

Algorithm 3: Get_Reg_Vaccine 0x5B38Da6a701c568545dCfE875f56beddC4 (from) 0xd8b934580fdE35a11B58C6D73aDeE468a2833fa8 (to Vaccine registration smart contract)	
Step 1	: if (vaccine quality meet the requirements) (Transaction Hash) 0x1a40b76c6ecdb399dcfb28e80d1ca5866c671fde49a6d24047cedf989b236bf5
Step 2	: Then check Msg.sender address == unique_account_address return true
Step 3	: else return false
Step 4	: End
Algorithm 4: Vaccine detailed information 0x5B38Da6a701c568545dCfE875f56beddC4 (from) 0xf8e81D47203A594245E36C48e151709F0C19fBe8 (to Consumer Smart contract)	
Input	: Vaccine name
Output	: Vaccine information Transaction Hash (0xd7289f338801ebb0ebc5c6c1652965788eb646856289cb08639c3a5bd18f2e77)
Step 1	: if Msg.sender vaccine_name == vaccine_name
Step 2	: show (_mediName,company_name,approval_status,mamu_date,expi_date)
Step 3	: Else return false
Step 4	: End

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Private vs. public blockchain

A **private blockchain** gives more security and control:

- only the authenticated nodes are allowed to access the network,
- a new user can only be added when the owner of the private blockchain allows it.
- Only those nodes who have been given the rights during the configuration of the genesis block will be able to mine.

A **public blockchain** is a platform that allows anyone to be part of the network: it is open to everyone by nature.

However, the offline unique account address we added makes the network admit only those users who have a UA.

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Evaluation

Typical criteria are

- Transaction Gas Cost
- Number of Blocks Lost
- Block Propagation Time
- Transactions Per Second

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Transaction Gas Cost of Ethereum Smart Contracts and Functions

Smart Contracts	Transaction Gas Cost	Ether Cost	Price (USD)	Price (Pounds)
Vaccine Registration	453152	0.0380648	\$149.70	92.48
Regulatory Authority	303125	0.0254625	\$100.14	46.90
Consumer	103531	0.0084895	\$ 33.07	23.85
Functions				
Get_Reg_Company	100235	0.0082193	\$ 32.022	23.08
Check_approved_UniqAddr	8132	0.0006668	\$ 2.59	1.87
Get_Reg_Vaccine	50120	0.0026075	\$16.01	11.54
Vaccine_complete_info	8053	0.0007481	\$ 2.91	2.10

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Transaction Gas Cost of Ethereum Smart Contracts and Functions

- The total gas cost to deploy all three smart contracts on the Ethereum public network is 859,808, ca. 280 USD.
- This total gas cost is required only for the deployment of the smart contracts and only once. It is quite affordable.
- Functions are very affordable in terms of gas costs.
- The consumer uses most of the time the *vaccine_complete_info* function: it uses very little gas (\$2.91): this shows how efficient TISVSchain is computationally.
- Other smart contracts like *get_reg_vaccine* cost almost \$32 to the company that wants to manufacture some vaccine and needs approval from the regulatory authority.
- For a company to check whether the offline unique account address is registered or not, *check_approved_uniqaddr* costs \$1.87. This shows TISVSchain is effectively efficient in performance and cost.

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How efficient is it?

Block-Time	Lost Blocks when Number of Sealers are				
	1 st Sealer	2 nd Sealer	3 rd Sealer	4 th Sealer	5 th Sealer
5s	38	40	87	102	132
10s	15	16	42	79	91
15s	18	17	35	71	88
20s	8	13	28	67	76
25s	11	14	25	61	68

Lost (or Orphan) blocks are blocks mined at the same time as another block but not accepted by the blockchain.

Longer block times give more time to sealers to get the data, to check it, and sign the transaction.

Lost blocks increase with sealer number because when a signed block broadcasts, the new blocks proposed by the backup sealers become obsolete, which causes the lost blocks.

To accept a block to become part of the blockchain network, **>50% of sealer verification** is needed.

Because of the synchronization issues caused by lost blocks, it takes longer to accept a block.

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How fast is it?

Block-Time	Lost Blocks when Number of Sealers are				
	1 st Sealer	2 nd Sealer	3 rd Sealer	4 th Sealer	5 th Sealer
5s	38	40	87	102	132
10s	15	16	42	79	91
15s	18	17	35	71	88
20s	8	13	28	67	76
25s	11	14	25	61	68

Propagation delay is the difference between the time a node announces the discovery of a new block and the time when other nodes receive that information.

By increasing the number of sealers the number of lost blocks increases, therefore the propagation delay also increases, and this delay can cause synchronization issues in the network (between the nodes).

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How fast is it?

- **Transactions per second (TPS)** are higher with shorter block times.
- But shorter block times increase the block loss, so there is a trade-off.
- A higher gas limit (= accepted cost) gives a higher TPS.

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Conclusions

- **TISVChain** is a framework based on blockchain to handle the issues of counterfeits vaccine and vaccine supply chain problems like transparency, immutability, and traceability
- Public blockchain: implemented using REMIX IDE (for Ethereum), smart contracts (in the Solidity language), very low gas cost
- Improves security: added offline unique account addresses (UA) to public blockchain-based frameworks
- improves overall efficiency of the framework
 - keeping the gas cost low,
 - decreased number of lost blocks □ keep low propagation delay,
 - high TPS value (transactions per second)

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Thank you!

BC4
ECO

Appendix 7: Environmental Sustainability - TalTech

A Conceptual Framework for the Adoption of Block Chain Technology to Environmental Sustainability

Definitions of short-termism in technological change

- When managers' orientations to the short-term become excessive and they become more concerned with Short-term profits than the environmental sustainability or entity value, they are said to be short-termist (That is when they reduce or postpone long-term investments with a positive net present value. Managers behave irrationally)

A Conceptual Framework for the Adoption of Block Chain Technology to Environmental Sustainability

External short-term pressures

- “Pressures upon the managers of companies to use a shorter time horizon and/or apply a higher discount rate than they otherwise would, in the appraisal of technological investment decisions (broadly defined)”

Internal short term pressures

- “ Pressures put by the organisational structure and culture upon management, in particular at divisional and lower levels, to use a shorter time horizon and/or apply a higher discount rate above the cost of capital than they otherwise would in the appraisal of investment decisions for the environment and or sustainability”

3

A Conceptual Framework for the Adoption of Block Chain Technology to Environmental Sustainability

Determinants of external short-term pressures

	Pressures	
	Weak	Strong
1. Opportunity cost of capital	low	high
- interest rate on external funds	low	high
- firm's liquidity	high	low
2. Shareholder information	rich	thin
3. Dependence on shareholder evaluation	low	high
- takeover vulnerability	low	high
- need for external funding	low	high

4

A Conceptual Framework for the Adoption of Block Chain Technology to Environmental Sustainability

Determinants of external short-term pressures

	Pressures	
	Weak	Strong
4. Accounting standards for intangibles	weak	strict
5. Type of investment	tangible	intangible
6. Uncertainty of return	low	high

5

A Conceptual Framework for the Adoption of Block Chain Technology to Environmental Sustainability

Determinants of internal short-term pressures for technological innovation

1. Organisational structure
2. Organisational culture
3. Managers' perceptions of financial markets and analysts (short-term vs long-term)
4. Managers' reliance on accounting performance measures

6

A Conceptual Framework for the Adoption of Block Chain Technology to Environmental Sustainability

Conclusions

- No dominant financial and corporate system is appropriate to all industries, countries for Technological Innovation for the Environment.
- Sharp differences between developed and developing countries.
- Different types of Technological Change may require different financial systems.

Areas for future work

- Use multiple measures of performance.
- Emphasize sustainability as a long-term performance and strategy.
- Recognize “knowledge” and “environment” as an economic resource in company accounts.
- Improve communication and understanding within firm and with institutional investors and other stakeholders.

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A Conceptual Framework for the Adoption of Block Chain Technology to Environmental Sustainability

Research issues

- Continue to connect academic theories to real world practice of Technological change and sustainability for the environment.
- Use field work with mini case studies.
- Focus on national culture with connections to institutions.
- Link strategy research to performance control, sustainability and their consequences.

8

Case Studies

- Technology plays an important role in combating environmental problems.
- Specifically **Block Chain Technology** can be used as a powerful tool dealing with various ecological aspects.
- Nowadays, there are several companies that implemented BC and other advanced IT solutions to solve environmental issues, e.g. plastic pollution.
- Further we will discuss the problem of plastic pollution and some examples implemented technologies.

9

Plastics and Microplastics

- **Plastic** is a very versatile material with a wide range of applications from product packaging to medical equipment.
- It represents between 50 - 80% of all items found in the environment.
- This material takes a long time to fragment and degrade under environmental conditions.

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Plastics and Microplastics

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Plastics and Microplastics

- However, influenced by solar radiation, temperature, and abrasion, larger plastic items fragment over time into smaller items known as **microplastics**.
- **Microplastics** are any synthetic, solid particle or polymeric matrix with regular or irregular shape, with size ranging between 1 μm and 5 mm, of either primary or secondary origin, which is insoluble in water

Frias and Nash, 2019, Marine Pollution Bulletin

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Microplastics

Where does plastic accumulate in the ocean?

Macroplastics are greater than 0.5cm in diameter
Microplastics are smaller than 0.5cm

Our World
in Data

Data source: Lebreton et al. (2019). A global mass budget for positively buoyant macroplastic debris in the ocean. This is a visualization from OurWorldinData.org, where you find data and research on the world's largest problems.

Licensed under CC-BY by the author Hannah Ritchie.

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Microplastics

Microplastics in the surface ocean, 1950 to 2050

Microplastics are buoyant plastic materials smaller than 0.5 centimeters in diameter. Future global accumulation in the surface ocean is shown under three plastic emissions scenarios: (1) emissions to the oceans stop in 2020; (2) they stagnate at 2020 emission rates; or (3) continue to grow until 2050 in line with historical plastic production rates.

Our World
in Data

Source: Lebreton et al. (2019). A global mass budget for positively buoyant macroplastic debris in the ocean. OurWorldinData.org/plastic-pollution • CC BY

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Microplastics - Impacts

- Microplastics might have impacts on environmental and human health, but so far there are not a lot of researches assessing the health effects or risks associated with microplastic ingestion.
- Several studies are reporting oxidative stress, DNA damage, inflammation, and other health-related issues induced by the microplastics pollution in the human body.
- EPA of Ireland provides a Research Report on Impacts of Microplastics in the **Irish Freshwater Environment**.
- The study has produces data on the biological impacts of microplastics on two representative freshwater species in Ireland:

Lemna minor (duckweed)

Gammarus duebeni (freshwater amphipod).

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Microplastics - Impacts

Impacts and fate of microplastics in the freshwater environment. Microplastics are adsorbed to aquatic plants and ingested and fragmented by amphipods.

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Microplastics - Impacts

- It was found that freshwater systems do not just transport plastics from land to the marine environment; they **are microplastic pollution sinks**. The following three conclusions are highlighted:
 1. Microplastics adhere to plant surfaces, resulting in a risk of trophic transfer into the food chain.
 2. Microplastics rapidly fragment into nanoplastics with unknown environmental impacts.*
 3. Microfibres can be found in the gut of invertebrates.

*This changes the belief that microplastics are stable in the environment for long periods of time.

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Microplastics - Removal

- To process microplastics (biodegradation, incineration, etc.), they must be removed first.
- Removal can be performed by various enrichment options (adsorption, filtration, etc.) (*Pan et al, 2023*)
- Irish environmentalist Fionn Ferreira created a new unique way to remove microplastics using **Ferrofluid**, a magnetic liquid mixture, which binds to microplastic particles, separating them from water and allowing for their removal using magnets.
- It can be used safely in drinking water, the process does not require filters, and it produces zero waste. It retains nearly all the magnetic liquid while removing microplastics.

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Example 1

- **Circular** (<https://www.circular.com>) company is using blockchain technology creating more sustainable, ethical, and transparent supply chains.
- It maps supply chains for companies pursuing greener, more sustainable production.
- They can track the lifecycles of materials such as plastics effectively, what leads to more responsible and closed-loop recycling systems.

Example 2

- A fruitful collaboration of UL and TUS resulted in a project, whose focus is on identification of different quantities and types of microplastics presented in Shannon River.
- Identification of the morphology and the chemical composition of the microplastics was performed using Microscopy (optical and SEM) and spectroscopy (RAMAN and FTIR).
- Then, to determine the distribution of microplastics corresponding to different input parameters, an empirical model using the artificial neural network (ANN) was developed.

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Example 2

Identification of Microplastic in Shannon River using SEM, spectroscope and Machine Learning

OPEN ISSUES

- 170 TRILLION OF MICROPLASTICS IN THE OCEAN PER YEAR*
- PRESENCE OF MICROPLASTICS IN FRESH ANTARTIC SNOW
- DETRIMENTAL IMPACT ON THE LIVING ORNANISMS
- PRIMARY SOURCES: TEXTILE AND INDUSTRIES

PROJECT OUTLINES

Step1:
Samples collection from the Shannon River

Step2:
Categorization of the type and amount of microplastics

Step3:
Development of an effective artificial neural network model for identifying microplastics

*<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0281596>

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Appendix 8: Case Study on Identification of Microplastic in Shannon River using SEM, Spectroscopy, and Machine Learning

Identification of Microplastic in Shannon River using SEM, Spectroscopy, and Machine Learning

Introduction:

The extensive utilization of plastics has given rise to significant concerns regarding the proliferation of microplastic pollution in various organisms, including edible crops and vegetables, due to their minute size. Moreover, several studies are reporting oxidative stress, DNA damage, inflammation, and other health-related issues induced by the microplastics pollution in the human body [1]. Microplastics encompass a range of sizes, ranging from nanometers to the dimensions of a grain of rice. The primary origins of microplastic pollution are attributed to industries, textiles, and various other contributors, including cosmetic industries [2]. Microplastics undergo fragmentation, resulting in the generation of microplastics from these sources, which subsequently infiltrate freshwater systems and ultimately find their way into larger water bodies such as oceans and seas. Remarkably, microplastic pollution has even reached polar regions, underscoring the pressing need to develop identification techniques for assessing the nature and quantity of microplastics in diverse sources [3].

General Overview of the Project:

The focus of this project is to identify the various types and quantities of microplastics present in the Shannon River. This project is coming from a fruitful collaboration between the UL and TUS (Molish Campus). Microscopy (optical and SEM) and spectroscopy (RAMAN and FTIR) will be used to identify the morphology and the chemical composition of the microplastics present inside the water of the Shannon River. Later, an empirical model using the artificial neural network (ANN) which determines the distribution of microplastics corresponding to different input parameters (volume of soil/sample, moisture content) will be developed. This model in future can be used to identify different microplastics and the volume of microplastic in the sample, and hence preventative measures will be offered based on the categorization (inputs from the samples) of microplastics. Data collected from experimental data and ANN models will be used to develop guidelines for the citizens of Limerick. These guidelines will help people avoid health issues caused by consuming microplastics through drinking water and take necessary precautions to protect their health and well-being. This research will provide valuable insights into the extent of microplastic pollution in Ireland's water bodies and help inform policymakers and stakeholders about the urgent need to address this issue. The preliminary results of this research will be useful to environmental scientists in Ireland, as they can leverage this information to develop novel techniques for removing microplastics from river water. This investigation can also serve as a foundation for future studies aimed at mitigating the impact of microplastics on aquatic ecosystems and human health. Moreover, this analysis will yield valuable insights for establishing guidelines aimed at reducing microplastic contamination, aligning with the UN Sustainable Development Goal of "Conserving and sustainably using oceans, seas, and marine resources for sustainable development" ([THE 17 GOALS | Sustainable Development \(un.org\)](https://www.un.org/sustainabledevelopment/)). By gaining a comprehensive understanding of the underlying mechanisms of microplastic pollution, this study aims to prevent associated adverse effects and health ailments. Recently, the project was awarded a research grant of 10,000 euros by the UL citizens' assembly on May 25, 2023 (Figure 1). This initiative places a strong emphasis on actively involving the local community, particularly primary school students, to enhance awareness regarding the problem of microplastic pollution and its potential consequences for future generations. Furthermore, it showcases the proactive engagement of the UL scientific community with the local residents.

Figure 1: Left Dr. Michela Ottaviani (Lecturer, Department of Physics UL), Dr. Amit Haldar (Lecturer, Department of Mechanical and Automobile Engineering TUS), Dr. Anita Chatterjee (Medical Doctor) and Dr. Mehakpreet Singh (Lecturer, Department of Mathematics and Statistics UL)

Details of the Project:

The project will be developed in three different phases: 1) Engagement of primary schools for the sample collection, 2) Sample analysis and machine learning techniques, 3) Solutions for the stakeholder.

Primary school engagement:

Ten schools (6th class primary schools), especially from rural areas, will be offered to visit the University of Limerick and be hosted by the Bernal Institute to perform one-day scientific program. The SSPC Centre will facilitate access to a lab that is specifically equipped for hosting the primary school students (20 per visit).

The students will be guided through the experimental part by watching an introductory video about the water samples collection from the Shannon River inside the UL.

Figure 2: Water sampling station (Indicated with the arrow).

The surface water samples (0.50 m depth) will be collected only from an identified sampling station in the UL (Figure 2), with a 10 L stainless steel bucket, transferred to glass bottles, and immediately carried to the laboratory in refrigerated boxes.

The distribution of microplastics is influenced by meteorological, temporal, and geographical factors. Moreover, environmental variable such as water density, wind, currents, and waves exert a significant role in their dispersion [4].

Therefore, during each sample collection, we will record meteorological condition (obtained from [Met Éireann - The Irish Meteorological Service](#)), water flux (Figure 3) and water temperature.

Figure 3: Flow meter.

The quantity and quality of microplastics are greatly influenced by both the sampling location and depth, with distribution being affected by the hydrodynamic profiles. According to the literature [4], it is expected that a density of approximately 1.00 g/cm^3 of microplastics will be observed in freshwater.

A 100 ml water sample will be collected from the glass bottles in the lab from the students (Figure 4a). To ensure an accurate identification and characterization of microplastic components, an essential preliminary step is the removal of other interfering organic materials [4]. This will be achieved through a simple and well-established digestive protocol [5] using hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) performed by the students (Figure 4b). Following chemical digestion, the microplastics will be separated from any remaining sediments or other inorganic substances (see Figure 4c). It has been demonstrated that these components can effectively be removed using NaCl, a non-toxic, abundant, and cost-effective salt [5]. The further step in microplastics isolation will be a filtration process, achieved by passing the water through a stack of sieves with mesh of different dimensions (Figure 4d).

It is expected that the microplastics can be classified as: (i) large microplastics of size ranging between 5 mm to 1 mm, (ii) small microplastics of 1 mm to $1 \mu\text{m}$ size range, and (iii) nanoplastics of $<1 \mu\text{m}$ size [6]. Finally, the microplastics will be categorized according to the size (Figure 4e).

This preliminary screening will play a crucial role in gathering information about the size, type, and density of every class of microplastics within the initial water volume.

Figure 4: Experimental procedure for the microplastic isolation and classification.

Samples analysis and machine learning (ANN modeling):

It is well known in literature that the different type of microplastics presents different shapes [2]. For example (Figure 5) polystyrene typically presents a spherical form while polyester has a filiform structure. With the help of an optical microscope, each type of microplastics will be identified and classified according to the size and shape.

Figure 5: Microplastics photographed before and after enzymatic and alkaline digestion. Alkaline hydrolysis resulted in structural damage to nylon fibers, melding of polyethylene fragments, and discoloration to uPVC granules. Magnification: polystyrene spheres $\times 40$; nylon line $\times 20$; polyester fiber $\times 63$; polyethylene granules $\times 200$; uPVC powder $\times 160$ [2].

To enhance the analysis, optical microscopy is often combined with spectroscopic techniques. This complementary approach enables simultaneous identification and quantification of microplastics. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) is widely employed to gather information about the morphology (dimension and shape) of microplastics and for enhancing the understanding of the surface characteristics. In addition, the SEM can detect both organic and inorganic elements that are attached to the surface of microplastics. This capability allows for a comprehensive analysis of the microplastics surface composition, providing valuable insights into potential interactions and environmental implications. The microscope can be equipped with additional detectors for the EDS (Energy Dispersive X-ray-Spectroscopy) analysis for qualitative and quantitative elemental analysis on the samples. SEM-EDS proves valuable in swiftly distinguishing between non-plastic and plastic particles, as well as detecting particles that might be overlooked through visual and optical detection methods [5, 7]. Figure 6 displays typical SEM images of different morphology of microplastics and their corresponding EDS spectra. Fourier-transform infrared (FT-IR) and Raman spectroscopy are powerful techniques capable of identifying various polymers through their unique vibrational spectra, which act as distinct "fingerprints" for each polymer type [2, 5, 7]. FT-IR is proficient in characterizing microplastics within the range of 5 mm to 500 μm , while $\mu\text{-FTIR}$ can achieve even higher resolution down to 10 μm . On the other hand, $\mu\text{-Raman}$ spectroscopy is capable of detecting microplastics as small as 1 μm , making it a valuable tool for analyzing the tiniest microplastics in environmental samples [2, 5, 7, 8].

Figure 6: Fig. 5. Two polymer types of MPs (PE, PP) with different morphologies (fibers, films, fragments) were examined under a SEM-EDS instrumentation. Their morphological analysis is provided in figures comprised by the EDS spectra of particles [7].

Figure 7: FT-IR spectra of microplastics particles found in surface waters at the Bahía Blanca Estuary: (a) cellulose-based textile, (b) poly(acrylonitrile-co-methyl acrylate) copolymeric, (c) polyethylene terephthalate, (d) poly(propylene), (e) polyester/alkyd resins, and (f) poly(ethylene-co-vinyl acetate) [9].

Figure 8: Raman spectra. Library spectrum of copper phthalocyanine (blue) and the spectrum of a particle identified as copper phthalocyanine in a sample from the educational institution [10].

The literature encompasses an extensive examination of microplastics in drinking water, freshwater sources, and wastewater, spanning multiple geographical regions, including Asia, Australia, Europe, and North America. In Figure 9, the number of studies documenting specific microplastic shapes is depicted, with fragments being the most frequently detected shape. Figure 10 records the number of studies that report particular polymer types of microplastics, with polyethylene (PE) and polypropylene (PP) emerging as the most prevalent polymer types documented.

Figure 9: Number of studies reporting a particular shape of microplastic particles (from a total of 55 records)[11].

Figure 10: number of studies reporting a particular polymer type of microplastic particles (32 out of 55 record reported polymer type) [11].

Experimental data collection serves as the foundation for training and validating Artificial Neural Network (ANN) models, enabling them to learn complex relationships within the data. ANN modeling, in turn, leverages these insights to make predictions and uncover hidden patterns, enhancing our understanding and decision-making in various fields, from finance to environmental science [12]. ANN model is comprised of three layers including input, hidden, and outcome layers. The influencing factors are included in the input layer, while the hidden layer is composed of many layers with different numbers of nonlinear neurons that connect the input and output layers (refer to Figure 1).

The hidden layers are formed by the activation function or transfer function, a differentiable nonlinear function that is more effective at modeling complex processes than a network trained with a linear function. Normally, the hidden layers use the same kind of activation function. There are three type of activation function: Rectified linear activation (ReLu), logistics (Sigmod), hyperbolic tangent (Tanh).

Figure 11: A typical neural network architecture.

ANN modeling for microplastics distribution in water is a valuable tool in understanding and predicting the complex behavior of microplastics in aquatic environments. ANN models can incorporate a range of input parameters, such as water currents, temperature, and microplastics characteristics, to simulate their dispersion and concentration patterns. By training ANN models on historical data and observed patterns, researchers can gain insights into the factors influencing microplastics distribution and make predictions about their future spread in various water bodies. This modeling approach aids in environmental assessment, risk analysis, and the development of strategies to mitigate microplastic pollution, contributing to the protection of aquatic ecosystems and human health [13].

Solution for stakeholders:

The grant not only provides us with an initial project budget but also offers a valuable opportunity to showcase our work through UL's social media platforms, significantly boosting our visibility. This success has expanded our network, attracted not only academic and research partners but also generated interest from industrial collaborators. Recently, a promising opportunity has emerged for collaboration with a well-established Irish company to develop water purification infrastructure. Additionally, in partnership with TUS, we have applied for an SFI infrastructure grant aimed at creating a center of excellence in Limerick and fostering increased collaboration between the two universities. This is expected to attract more industrial partners eager to be part of this innovative initiative. Moreover, I am currently involved in a collaborative project with colleagues at UL, centered around the innovative repurposing of microplastics retrieved from an Irish water purification facility. Our objective is to transform these discarded microplastics into valuable materials for use in Li-ion batteries. This groundbreaking initiative holds the potential to serve as a prominent exemplar of a circular economy in Ireland, setting an inspiring precedent for other European nations.

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Additional Information (useful links):

1. [Microplastics \(europa.eu\)](https://europe.ec.europa.eu/en/microplastics)
2. [Drinking water | Environmental Protection Agency \(epa.ie\)](https://www.epa.gov/drinking-water)
3. [Regulating energy and water for a changing climate | CRU.ie](https://www.cru.ie/en/research/energy-and-water-for-a-changing-climate/)

Appendix 9: Solving Wicked Problems: Design Thinking and Systems Thinking - AAU

Second Summer School

Limerick,
21. September 2023

Solving Wicked Problems:
Design Thinking and Systems-thinking

Amalia de Götzen and Andy Perucco
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BC4ECO has received funding from the Erasmus+ cooperation partnerships in higher education, under grant Agreement No KA220-HED-2021-003

The SDLAB - AAU

- We run the master's programme in Service Systems Design (some 30 students per year)
- We are active on research projects (5+ EU projects + 2 NordForsk projects) and publications (20+ publications per year)
- 11 members

WE RESEARCH AND APPLY SERVICE DESIGN AS AN EXPLORATORY, CO-CREATIVE AND EMPOWERING APPROACH TO ADDRESS ISSUES OF SOCIETAL CONCERN.

What is BC4ECO

What types of challenges are we facing?

Environmental challenges are wicked and complex and require a **multidisciplinary**, **problem-based**, **systemic** and **decentralised** perspective in order to tackle them.

We aim at thinking how Distributed Ledger Technologies (**DLTs**) can be critically assessed to address some of the environmental challenges affecting our society.

3

BC4ECO approach

4

BC4ECO approach

5

Concepts developed within the first Summer School

Within the school, students had the opportunity to envision an ecosystem that utilised blockchain technology. **Without delving into the implementation details** of Distributed Ledger Technologies (DLTs), they were able to explore the potential power dynamics that could arise from adopting this technology in the context of environmental sustainability challenges.

6

6

Ecosystem map

Trust Loop

INSPIRATION BOARD

RELEVANT RESOURCES

Group 1

Group 2

Group 3

Group 4

Group 5

8

What are wicked problems?

1. There is no definitive formula for a wicked problem.
2. Wicked problems have no stopping rule, as in there's no way to know your solution is final.
3. Every wicked problem is essentially unique.
4. Every wicked problem can be considered a symptom of another problem.
5. There is always more than one explanation for a wicked problem because the explanations vary greatly depending on the individual perspective.

9

Thinking in Systems

“Systems surprise us because our minds like to think about single causes neatly producing single effects. We like to think about one or at most a few things at a time. And we don’t like, especially when our own plans and desires are involved, to think about limits. But we live in a world in which many causes routinely come together to produce many effects. (...)”

For example, an industrial manufacturing process needs:

- capital
- labor
- energy
- raw materials
- land
- water
- technology
- credit
- insurance
- customers
- good management
- **public-funded infrastructure** and government services (such as police and fire protection and education for managers and workers)
- **functioning families** to bring up and care for both producers and consumers
- a healthy **ecosystem to supply or support all these inputs and to absorb or carry away their wastes**”

Excerpt From Thinking in Systems: A Primer, Donella H. Meadows

10

Thinking in Systems

When dealing with Wicked Problems, we might find how one specific problem is entangled and interconnected with so many others

Before starting to identify solutions for complexity, it is necessary to map it!

11

Systemic design: what is designed?

14

System design

In systems design, what is being designed is a system, the intention is to give that system some particular properties, and the system boundaries can be objectively defined.

Systems that are completely 'designable' are often technical systems designed by systems engineers.

System design ≠ Systemic design

15

System-conscious design

In system-conscious design, what is designed is a **product or service with the intention to produce a certain function**, taking into account its potential 'side-effects' on a larger subjectively defined system, such as its effect on communities, society, economy and the environment.

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System-shifting design

Where system-conscious design is aimed at designing products and services without adverse systemic effects, system-shifting design has a radically different intention, namely to shift systems into a desired direction.

For example designing for the protein shift to develop a more sustainable food system, or shifting the academic system to improve wellbeing of students and staff.

What are the leverage points of the systems? (Donella Medow)

17

How systemic designers work with those intentions?

18

1) Systemic design visualizations

One of the more well-known approaches to systemic design is the use of systemic visualisations.

These can take many shapes and forms, each with their own underlying systems theories, for example stakeholder relational maps, causal loop diagrams, social network analysis, and mapping system layers with [the iceberg model of system structures](#).

Visualisations are used as a **systemic sense making** tool and as inspiration for a design process.

Check this resources out: [systemic design toolkit](#) and Birger Sevaldson's [giga-mapping](#)

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Systemic design visualizations

Emerging Trends and patterns

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Systemic design visualizations

Policies, Laws, Physical structures

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Systemic design visualizations

Mindset, values and assumptions

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2) Designing from within

The 'designing from within' perspective perceives systems as being **continuously designed and redesigned from the inside out**.

It acknowledges that each system has 'residents' that design their work, tools, way of life and environment without necessarily calling it 'design'.

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3) Systemic design reasoning

Design reasoning is the cognitive practice and 'logic' that is at the core of any design process and is aimed at **aligning design intentions to a matching design.**

It includes framing and 'co-evolution of problem and solution'

Designers often use a **range of methods and tools** to support this reasoning process, including metaphors, human-centred design methods, prototyping and more.

In systemic design reasoning, this approach is combined with systems theory and practices, supported by, for example, [systemic design principles](#) and systemic design methods.

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How to apply systemic thinking to our case?

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Wicked or not? What do we want to do?

- What is the problem?
- Is it a wicked problem?
 - If so why?
- Are you designing a system?
- Is your design system conscious?
- Are you trying to shift the system in a given direction?

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Resources

<https://medium.com/@miekevanderbijl/systems-thinking-design-72209d534c4c>

Bijl-Brouwer, M. van der, & Malcolm, B. (2020). Systemic Design Principles in Social Innovation: A Study of Expert Practices and Design Rationales. *She Ji: The Journal of Design, Economics, and Innovation*, 6(3), 386–407.

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Appendix 10:Blockchain Concept and Example - UL

Blockchain

Blockchain

A Blockchain is a replicated database, managed by a consensus mechanism, in a peer-to-peer network of non-trusting parties

- Blockchain can be simply defined as a **time-stamped** series of data **records** that are managed by a cluster of **nodes**.
- Nodes are computers that are connected in a peer-to-peer network and have an identical copy of the data.
- A new data entry is validated and transmitted to the entire network to maintain the identical copy of the database.

Blockchain as a data structure

- The blockchain **data structure** consists of a **chain of blocks**.
- Each block records **transactions** validated in a particular period that have not yet been recorded in any prior blocks.
- These blocks are linked to one another through a **cryptographic hash** such that each subsequent block contains the hash of the previous block (also called parent) header and hence constitutes a chain.
- The first block, known as the **genesis block**, has no reference to a previous block since it has no parent block.
- This **linkability** is a cryptographic mechanism that maintains data integrity and immutability in the network.

Recording transactions

A transaction goes through multiple steps in a Blockchain network before it is validated by the network.

1. A user digitally signs and submits its information as a transaction.
2. The transaction is broadcast to the entire network, where each neighboring node conducts validation for the transaction before relaying it to the next node.
3. The transaction is collected and validated by a validator (sealer), who includes it in a new proposed block.
4. The consensus mechanism determines the validator who has the right to propose his block to the network.
5. Once other nodes validate the block, the block will be added to the chain, and the block will be propagated to all nodes to allow these nodes to update their database.
6. After being recorded in the blockchain, the transaction is considered complete and henceforth consumed by its new owner.

Public, private, and consortium blockchains

Blockchains can be classified into public, private, and consortium blockchain based on their settings.

A **Public Blockchain** is permissionless if the platform is publicly open for users without permission from any authority. Generally, in a public blockchain all transactions are visible to the public. Bitcoin is a well-known example of a public blockchain.

A **Private Blockchain** is not entirely open for the public to use: a centralized authority controls and defines who has the right to join the network.

Thus a private blockchain is considered to be centralized due to the fact that a single authority maintains the network.

Besides, data in a private blockchain is prone to tampering.

Examples of private blockchain: Corda, Hyperledger Fabric, and Hyperledger Sawtooth.

Public, private, and consortium blockchains

A **Consortium Blockchain** has different organizations involved to manage a shared blockchain.

The authority is distributed among different organizations, thus the consortium blockchain is considered to have *semi-decentralized* management and governance.

In a consortium blockchain,

- only a preselected set of nodes participates in the consensus process.
- a limited number of trusted participants are required to validate the block.

This is what makes the consortium blockchain highly scalable and guarantees high throughput.

A consortium blockchain is best suitable for organizational collaboration.

Ethereum

Ethereum is a stateful blockchain-based computing platform **with smart contract** functionality that lets users build **decentralized applications** running on blockchain technology.

Besides the distributed ledger, Ethereum provides a **virtual machine**, called the Ethereum Virtual Machine (EVM), which can execute scripts written in a high-level **programming language** (e.g., Solidity).

In Ethereum, the blockchain data structure is more complex than in its predecessor, Bitcoin.

Ethereum: data structure

The **block's header** comprises metadata,

Its **body** comprises multiple types of data, namely:

- transactions,
- receipts, and
- system states (account states).

Each of these data types is organized into a Merkle tree or a Patricia tree (Radix tree) in the state tree.

The **state tree** (or the account Storage tree) is an essential component in the Ethereum ledger.

It is used to implement the **account model**, whereby each account is linked to its related states (account balances, smart contract states, etc.).

Any node can parse the tree using the account address and get the updated state without any overhead calculation.

The state tree grows each time a change occurs in a state. It grows by adding new nodes (stored in the new block) — holding new states— which point to the nodes (stored in the previous block) containing the old value for the same state.

To enforce immutability, Ethereum keeps its root hash in the block header.

This tree manages two kinds of accounts:

- An **Externally Owned Account (EOA)** is an account controlled by a private key held by a given user. It has no associated code, and can send transactions.
- A **Contract Account** has an associated (smart contract) code that executes when it receives a transaction from an EOA.

Both accounts are represented by a cryptographically generated address of 20 bytes.

Ethereum costs

To prevent Denial-of-Service (DoS) attack, EVM adopts the gas system: every computation of a program must be paid for upfront in a dedicated unit called **gas** as defined by the protocol.

If the provided amount of gas does not cover the cost of execution, the transaction fails.

The block size is controlled by the **gas-limit**, which the miners (i.e. producers of new blocks) define, and a constant rise of the gas-limit happens.

In decentralized systems like Ethereum, we need to ensure that everyone agrees on the order of transactions. Miners help this happen by **solving computationally difficult puzzles to produce blocks, securing the network from attacks.**

Appendix 11: Organizational Collaboration Using Blockchain - UL

Organizational Collaboration Using Blockchain

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No KA220-HED-2021-003

Content

- ◆ Introduction of Blockchain
- ◆ Blockchain for Organizational Collaboration
- ◆ Design of Architecture
 - ❖ Prototyping of architecture using Visual paradigm (**Day Two**)
 - ❖ Guided Technical Tutorial for Blockchain Implementation (**Day Two**)
 - ❖ Conclusion

Introduction

Blockchain is

- ❖ This technology forms the foundation for cryptocurrencies like Bitcoin
- ❖ It has applications in various industries beyond **finance**, such as **supply chain**, **healthcare**, **environmental science** and more, and organizations collaboration.

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11036-020-01649-6>

3

Introduction

- ❖ Type of Blockchain
 - Public Blockchains
 - Private Blockchains
 - Hybrid Blockchains
 - Federated (or Consortium) Blockchains
 - Permissioned Blockchains
- ❖ Blockchain platforms
 - Smart Contract Platforms
 - Multi-Chain Platforms
 - Sidechains
 - Standalone Blockchains
 - Blockchain-as-a-Service (BaaS)
 - Bitcoin 2008

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Blockchain platforms

◆ Fabric

- Permitted blockchain hosted by Linux foundation
- Supports extensibility and modularity
- I have a channel feature which provides privacy
- Can be developed by different programming languages (JS,Java,Go)
- Smart contracts are referred to as chain codes in Fabric.

5

Introduction

- ❖ Blockchain is a method of storing data in blocks
- ❖ Relies on hashes and cryptography to secure the data
- ❖ Blocks reside on all computers in a peer-to-peer network
- ❖ Use the **consensus method** to verify transactions in the block
- ❖ Block consists of
 - List of transactions
 - Hash of the Block (a unique ID)
 - Hash of the previous Block

Data transactions

The hash of the Block change

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Hash Example

```

1 package SS2Limerick;
2
3 import java.util.Arrays;
4 //demonstrate has key
5 public class hash {
6     public static void main ( String[] args ) {
7         String[] list1 = { "ali", "peter", "david"};
8         String[] list2 = { "alsi", " peter", " david"};
9         System.out.println(Arrays.hashCode(list1));
10        System.out.println(Arrays.hashCode(list2));
11
12    }
13 }
14

```

Console x Problems Javadoc
 <terminated> hash [Java Application] C:\Users\Salim.Saay\p2\pool\plugins\org.eclipse.justj.openjdk.hot
 -803382171
 1235492296

Required Tools
 1- Java 17
 2- Eclipse Ide for
 Java developers

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Blockchain for Organizational Collaboration

- ❖ Use of blockchain technology to facilitate secure, transparent, and efficient cooperation across multiple organizations.
- ❖ To enhance trust, streamline processes, and enable shared access to information.
 - Immutable Recordkeeping
 - Decentralization
 - Smart Contracts
 - Permissioned Networks
 - Data Privacy and Security
 - Supply Chain Management
 - Cross-Organizational Workflows
 - Cost Reduction

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Blockchain for Organizational Collaboration

- ❖ How we use it in Organizational Collaboration
 - Organizations have their own database
 - Organizations have their own access rules and access policy
 - Organizations have their own law and procedures
 - We use Blockchain to provide collaboration by considering the existing rules in different organisations
 - A Permissioned Blockchain that can be accessible only to collaborators.

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System Architecture for Organizational Collaboration Using Blockchain

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Integration of Kafka (Broker)with Blockchain

- ❖ Open-source distributed event streaming platform
- ❖ Developed by LinkedIn , then joined Apache software foundation
- ❖ Distribute over numerous servers to guarantee high availability and fault tolerance
- ❖ Uses an publish –subscribe approach
- ❖ Uses TCP network protocol

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Integration of Kafka (Broker)with Blockchain

- ❖ KafKa and Fibrice are integrated via RestAPI

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System Architecture for Organizational Collaboration Using Block

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Authentication procedure with Blockchain

- ❖ We propose the Multi-Factor Self-Sovereign Identity Authentication (MFSSIA) protocol

Fig. 1 - General validation and authentication procedure (Leiding et al., 2016).

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Smart Contract

- ❖ Action taken on the blockchain data is limited by smart contract
- ❖ Smart contracts help solve real-world problems on the blockchain
- ❖ Smart contracts are deterministic, they execute the same on all nodes
- ❖ The access policy, rules and procedures need to be placed into smart contracts.

UML of the smart contract for organizational collaboration

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Supply Chain

- ❖ Supply chain is the path products or services take from producer to customer
- ❖ Intermediaries(middlemen) can increase the customer base for a product/service also drive the prices up
- ❖ Blockchain is an excellent solution for supply chain issues.
- ❖ Because there are so many participants in a supply chain, there are many oport for inefficient, nonstandard, and complicated issues to arise.
- ❖ Blockchain helps solve transparency and traceability issues since all nodes can transactions
- ❖ Smart contract in the blockchain helps solve transfer time lag, translation data lo: nonstandard status tracking since they establish the standard that needs to be fc by each participant.

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Thank you!

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ECO

Second Day

- ◆ Prototyping of architecture using Visual paradigm (Day Two)
- ◆ [School Collaboration System.vpd | Visual Paradigm Online \(visual-paradigm.com\)](#)

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Second Day

- ❖ Guided Technical Tutorial for Blockchain Implementation (Day Two)

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Appendix 12: Vision Zero and Blockchain: Data-Driven Framework for Resilient and Sustainable Road Safety - TalTech

Vision Zero and Blockchain: Data-Driven Framework for Resilient and Sustainable Road Safety

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Vision Zero

Vision Zero is a global movement to end traffic-related fatalities and serious injuries by taking a systemic approach to road safety. The premise of this strategy is that road deaths and injuries are unacceptable and preventable.

KPIs

► **EU ROAD SAFETY POLICY FRAMEWORK 2021-2030 - NEXT STEPS TOWARDS "VISION ZERO": HIGHLIGHTS THE NEED OF MEASURING ROAD SAFETY KPIs AT EUROPEAN LEVEL**

► **8 KPIs DIRECTLY RELATED TO THE PREVENTION OF ROAD ACCIDENT FATALITIES AND SERIOUS INJURIES (APPROVED BY HIGH LEVEL GROUP)**

Co2, Urban noise, fuel consumption

KPI speeding

Percentage of vehicles traveling within the speed limit

KPI Seatbelts and child restraint systems

Percentage of vehicle occupants using the safety belt or child restraint system correctly

KPI helmets of powered-two-wheelers and cyclists

Percentage of VRUs wearing protective helmets

KPI alcohol

Percentage of drivers within the legal limit for blood alcohol content

KPI Distraction using a handheld mobile device

Percentage of drivers not using a handheld mobile device

KPI vehicle safety

Percentage of passenger cars with Euro NCAP safety

KPI infrastructure

Percentage of high visibility signage and marking

KPI post-crash care

Time elapsed between the emergency call following a collision and the arrival at the scene of the collision of emergency services.

- Impact of variance in speed setting
- Very high percentage of non-compliance
- Direct cause of 30% of all fatalities
- => huge potential for accident reduction

- Drivers vs passengers
- Rear vs front
- 25% to 50% of fatally injured car occupants not wearing seatbelt
- 900 deaths per year could be avoided in the EU if 99% wearing rate

- **Field sobriety tests (FSTs)**
- 25% of all traffic fatalities (European Transport Safety Council- ETSC) ~ alcohol
- 1.5%-2% Drivers under influence (DUI) represents billions of kms of DUI /year, involving millions of drivers

LOW LATENCY ARCHITECTURE

VNF Networks Services

1. **Real-time Data Processing:** Fog nodes can process sensor data from vehicles in real-time to detect anomalies, such as sudden braking or lane departures, and alert drivers or other vehicles.
2. **Predictive Analytics:** Utilize machine learning algorithms to predict potential accidents or congestion based on historical and real-time data.
3. **Intrusion Detection and Prevention:** Implement security mechanisms at fog nodes to detect and prevent Cyberattacks on IoV, ensuring the integrity and safety of vehicle communications.
4. **Traffic Signal Optimization:** Use fog nodes to optimize traffic signal timings based on real-time traffic data to reduce congestion and improve traffic flow.
5. **Emergency Vehicle Priority:** Enable fog nodes to give priority to emergency vehicles, allowing them to pass through traffic more efficiently.
6. **Maintenance Predictions:** Use fog nodes for predictive maintenance, ensuring vehicles are in optimal condition for safe operation.

CLUSTER HEAD (CH) THE FIRST SELECTION

- To select the CH, we find the **neighbours** of each vehicles, then calculate a score and a **rank** for each of these vehicles.
- To calculate this rank, we use the Egocentric Betweenness Metric. In the future, other features will be added to refine this rank.
- The car with the best ranking becomes the CH and the second-placed car becomes the backup (CH backup), all other cars become Cluster Member (CM)

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CLUSTER HEAD (CH) CHOOSING OUR ALGORITHMS

- In many of the papers, they base their selection of the CH on the RSUs, but these are expensive and only have 300m communication.

- So we only consider them in the intersections

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CLUSTER HEAD (CH) THE RANK

- First: Discovering your neighbours from the position on sumo and communication range fixed according to IEEE 802.11p
- Second: Calculate your score based on the Egocentric Betweenness Metric (EBM) which depends on connections and neighbours

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CLUSTER HEAD (CH) RANKING - EBM

$$EBM_{(n)} = \sum_{A_n(i,j)=0, i < j} \frac{1}{A_n^2 [1 - A_n]_{i,j}}$$

So let's use the following situation, the example is centred on vehicle 1, vehicle 3 has the same connections as vehicle 1 but not vehicles 2 and 4.

This will create the matrix A with the columns and rows assigned to each vehicle

$$\text{The result is } A = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \text{ thus } A^2 = \begin{pmatrix} 3 & 1 & 2 & 1 \\ 1 & 2 & 1 & 2 \\ 2 & 1 & 3 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

Since the adjacency matrix A is symmetric and according to equation (1), only the non-zero values above the primary diagonal need to be analysed ($i < j$).

$$\text{So } A_n^2 [1 - A_n] = \begin{pmatrix} * & * & * & * \\ * & * & * & 2 \\ * & * & * & * \\ * & * & * & * \end{pmatrix} \text{ thus } EBM = \frac{1}{2} = 0.5$$

Ademar T Akabane, Roger Immich, Luiz F Bittencourt, Edmundo RM Madeira, and Leandro A Villas. Towards a distributed and infrastructure-less vehicular traffic managementsystem. Computer Communications, 151:306–319, 2020.

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CLUSTER HEAD (CH)

DIFFERENCE BETWEEN MAINTENANCE AND INITIALISATION IN SUMO

1.1) First initialisation (only V2V):

Input: Position, ID

- Role assignment according to the **rank** of these neighbours
- Need to calculate the rank for all vehicles.
- Very useful for cold starts: on SUMO, when no vehicle has an assignment, in the future, when resetting.

1.2) Maintains of CH and CHbck (only V2V):

Input: Position, ID, previous role/rank, speed

- Assigning a role according to the **role** of its neighbours
- Checking the speed of CHs and comparing it with the average **speed** of the cluster

In both cases, neighbours are detected

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CLUSTER HEAD (CH)

RESULTS ON SUMO

- **Red:** Cluster Head
- **Green:** Cluster Head Backup
- **Blue:** Cluster Member
- **Yellow:** Not taken into consideration
- **White:** If error

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EDGE LAYER

PREDICTION THE ARRIVAL VEHICLE

1.3) Prediction of the future direction: (V2V + V2I):

Input: Acceleration, position, speed

- Prediction of the next position in the intersection (Left, Front, Right) by the RSU
- Send the information to neighbor RSU to inform it to take into account the arrival of the vehicle

1.4) Verification of the direction (V2V + V2I):

Input: Position

- Verification of the position to reinforce the Kalman process
- Necessary to know the efficiency

- Currently no Kalman Filter
- Need to be improved by using the Kalman Filter

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CLUSTER HEAD (CH)

FUTURE

- RSUs analyze this information to select reliable and **trustworthy** vehicles as cluster heads (CH) within their coverage areas.
- The selection process considers factors such as **trust scores**, **communication reliability**, and **adherence to predefined security protocols**.

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Securing the CH Selection and Detecting Malicious Vehicles

FUTURE

- Evaluates the **trustworthiness** of vehicles based on their behavior, reputation, and interactions.
- Vehicles with **higher trust scores** are more likely to be selected as cluster heads.
- Machine learning or deep learning models to analyze data and **predict trust scores**.
- **Anomaly detection algorithms** identify any malicious activities or deviations from normal behavior that may indicate a malicious vehicle

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Securing the CH Selection and Detecting Malicious Vehicles

FUTURE

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Securing the CH Selection and Detecting Malicious Vehicles FUTURE

Malicious Vehicle Detection (IDPS)

- Monitors network traffic within the IoV architecture, including communication between vehicles and RSUs.
- Analyzes network packets, inspects data payloads, and compares them against known attack signatures or behavior patterns.
- Any vehicle exhibiting suspicious behavior or matching known attack patterns are identified as potentially malicious.
- Appropriate actions can be taken to mitigate the threat, such as isolating the malicious vehicle or blocking its communication.

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Securing the CH Selection and Detecting Malicious Vehicles FUTURE

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FOG LAYER – DATA ANALYSIS

•2.1) **Data Collection from Vehicles** : Vehicles equipped with sensors transmit real-time data, including speed, direction, acceleration, and other relevant parameters (e.g., HD videos).

- This data is collected by roadside infrastructure, such as RSUs, located strategically in the urban environment.

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FOG LAYER – DATA ANALYSIS

•2.2) **Data Processing and SDN Control**: The collected data is sent to the SDN controller, which acts as the central intelligence for decision-making.

- The SDN controller processes the data, analyzes it, and determines the current safety conditions based on predefined rules and algorithms.
- The SDN controller identifies potential collision risks, abnormal behaviors, or hazardous situations based on the received data.

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FOG LAYER – DEPLOY VNF FUNCTION

•2.3) **NFV Function Selection:** The SDN controller assesses the identified risks and determines the appropriate NFV functions to mitigate those risks.

- NFV functions can include **collision detection, collision prediction, emergency braking**, lane departure warning, adaptive cruise control, etc.
- The selection of NFV functions is based on the current safety conditions, the capabilities of the fog nodes (RSUs), and the overall system requirements.

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FOG LAYER – DEPLOY VNF FUNCTION

•2.4) **Fog Node (RSU) Deployment:** The SDN controller leverages its control over the fog computing infrastructure to deploy the selected NFV functions. It identifies the fog nodes (RSUs) in the vicinity that have the necessary computational resources, communication capabilities, and proximity to the vehicles involved.

- The NFV functions are deployed and instantiated on the selected fog nodes (RSUs) using **virtualization techniques**.
- The fog nodes (RSUs) now act as localized safety management points, ready to provide real-time safety services to the vehicles within their coverage area.

FOG LAYER – SECURE COMMUNICATION

2.5) Blockchain Integration: The deployed NFV functions on the fog nodes (RSUs) generate **safety-related events**

These events, along with relevant metadata (e.g., timestamp, vehicle information), are recorded as transactions on the Blockchain.

- o **Each fog node (RSU)** can participate as a node in the Blockchain network, contributing to the decentralized and distributed nature of the Blockchain.

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FOG LAYER – SECURE COMMUNICATION

2.6) Consensus and Verification: The Blockchain network achieves consensus among the participating nodes, ensuring the validity and integrity of recorded transactions.

- o The recorded transactions related to safety events are verified by multiple nodes in the network
- o Ensure **transparency**, and
- o Prevent **tampering**.

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FOG LAYER – PoA Consensus (1/2)

Proof of Authority: trusted validators with established identities validate transactions and create blocks:

- o **Energy Efficiency:** doesn't require resource-intensive computations
- o **Fast Transaction Speeds:** With known validators.
- o **Sybil Attack Resistance:** Since validators are reputable entities, the network is more resilient to Sybil attacks, where an attacker creates multiple fake identities.
- o **Governance and Trust:** PoA allows for controlled governance, as validator identities are established and trusted.

Leader node

$$\text{leader} = \left(\frac{\text{time} - \text{first}}{\text{step}} \right) \% \text{nodes}$$

- The new block is generated by a leader node of the current time interval.
- At each time interval, the leadership is passed to the next validating node from the list of validating nodes.

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FOG LAYER – PoA Consensus (2/2)

The **leader node** generates the new block as follows:

1. Collects all new transactions from its transaction queue.
2. Executes transactions one by one. Transactions that are invalid or cannot be executed are rejected.
3. Checks compliance to block generation limits.
4. Creates a block with valid transactions and signs it with node's private key (ECDSA algorithm).
5. Sends this block to other validating nodes.

Other validating nodes:

1. Receive the new block and validate that:
 - o The new block was generated by the leader node of a current interval.
 - o There are no other blocks generated by the leader node of a current interval.
 - o The block is generated and signed correctly.
2. Execute transactions from the block one by one. Check that transactions are executed successfully and within block generation limits.
3. Add or reject the block, depending on the previous step:
 - o If block validation is successful, add the new block to the node's blockchain.
 - o If block validation failed, reject the block and send a bad block transaction. If the validating node that created this invalid block continues to generate such blocks, it can be banned or excluded from the list of validating nodes.

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FOG LAYER – PoW Consensus (1/2)

Proof of Work: validate and secure transactions through **computational work** (solve complex mathematical puzzles).

- o **Security:** High computational power required to alter past blocks, making the blockchain resistant to tampering.
- o **Decentralization:** No single entity has control over the network. Miners from around the world participate, maintaining the decentralized nature of the blockchain
- o **Energy Intensive:** PoW consumes significant **amounts of electricity** due to the computational demands of mining.
- o **Difficulty Adjustment:** The network adjusts the difficulty of the puzzle-solving process to maintain a consistent block creation rate.

PoW is like a race between miners to solve a **cryptographic puzzle**

- Upon solving the puzzle, they win the chance to add the block to the chain and get rewarded.
- The cryptographic puzzle that miners race to solve is identifying the value of the nonce.
- A nonce is an attribute in the block header structure.

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FOG LAYER – PoW Consensus (2/2)

- **Miners** collect all pending transactions from the decentralized network and compete with each other to solve the puzzle.
- Whoever solves the puzzle will generate a block and push that block into the network for verification from other nodes, after which, the other nodes can add that block to their own copy of the blockchain.
- **Once a miner finds :**
 - o The nonce
 - o The collection of transactions
 - o The Merkle root of all transactions in the block and the nonce are broadcasted to the network for verification.
- Upon being notified, the other nodes from the network automatically check whether the results are valid.
 - o If the results are valid, they add the block to their copies of the blockchain, stop the mining work in hand, and move on to the next block.

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FOG LAYER – PoET Consensus (1/2)

Proof of Elapsed Time: Practical Byzantine Fault Tolerance.

- Designed to achieve consensus in distributed networks.
- Addresses the "Byzantine Generals Problem".
 - o **Energy Efficiency:** No resource-intensive calculations
 - o **Fairness:** Random selection prevents centralization
 - o **Security:** Sybil attacks and double spending mitigation
 - o **Scalability:** Suitable for large distributed networks

- The **PoET** mechanism replaces the need for mining intensive rights required in Proof of Work with a randomized timer system.
- The **PoET** consensus mechanism distributes the chances of winning across the largest possible number of network participants and every node is likely to be selected by a fair lottery system

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FOG LAYER – PoET Consensus (2/2)

The PoET consensus mechanism is divided into 2 phases:

- 1. Selection Process:** This process involves the following activities:
 - Every node in the network will share its certificate by Intel Software Guard Extension (SGX) which ensures the validity of the node to generate a new block in the network. After this, the node is eligible to get a timer object.
 - The numbers are assigned to each node as a timer object by Intel's RAND i.e. random number generator. RAND generates difficult-to-detect random numbers.
 - The time object given to each participating node activates.
- 2. Generation Process:** This process involves the following activities:
 - After the timer object expires and the node wakes up then the node is eligible to forge a new block to the network.
 - The active node generates the hash of its block of transactions and submits it for acceptance.
 - The update gets flooded to the network.

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FOG LAYER – ADAPTATION SYSTEM

2.7) Real-Time Safety Services: The deployed NFV functions on the fog nodes (RSUs) continuously process the incoming vehicle data in real-time. They perform tasks such as collision detection, risk assessment, and safety alerts based on the predefined algorithms and rules.

The safety services provided by the NFV functions aim to prevent collisions, warn drivers, or trigger autonomous safety measures (e.g., emergency braking) if required.

2.8) Feedback and System Adaptation: The SDN controller receives feedback from the deployed NFV functions, including collision alerts, status updates, or performance metrics.

Based on this feedback, the SDN controller can dynamically adapt the deployment of NFV functions, modify their configurations, or reassign them to different fog nodes (RSUs) for optimization.

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NETWORK SERVICES

Tasks Scheduler

- SDN controller receives tasks from various user devices to be executed on the fog nodes.
- Make on the task scheduler service by SDN controller to achieve the offloading of these tasks on fog nodes while optimizing the latency and minimizing the energy consumption.
- Task Scheduler service based on **Deep Reinforcement Learning** provides a better policy to assign tasks to fog nodes.

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Enhancing Decentralization of IoT Network with Blockchain

Main idea

- Three-layer IoT SDN-enabled architecture to efficiently distribute IoT tasks among available IoT devices
- DRL-based Task scheduler to improve task offloading
- Blockchain distributed ledger to reinforce the security, reliability, and resilience of IoT communication
- Security enabled through encrypted record of all IoT transactions

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Secure Communication

- Encryption function used to create and validate blocks
- Ensure decentralized communication between IoT nodes
- Smart contracts act as an agent for fog nodes and SDN controller

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Challenges

- ✓ **Data quality:** missing values, noisy data, data consistency.
- ✓ **Model explainability:** lack of interpretability and transparency.
- ✓ **Imbalanced data:** disproportionate samples for different classes.
- ✓ **High computation:** resource-intensive processing and analysis/Green computing for

embedded AI.

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Appendix 13: Visual Paradigm - UL

Visual Paradigm

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Limerick,
19th September 2023

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Introduction

- ❖ Visual Paradigm is a powerful tool used for visual modelling and design
- ❖ supports various modelling languages and methodologies, including:
 - Unified Modeling Language (UML),
 - Business Process Model and Notation (BPMN)
- ❖ We can install Visual Paradigm or use it online
- ❖ Visual paradigm is a good tool for project management

Introduction

◆ Project management tools

Agile project tools to improve productivity

Visual Paradigm features a rich set of Agile and Scrum tools for project management.

Project Management Tool
PM process map and roadmap tools. Agile, Scrum, PMBOK, etc.
[Learn more](#)

Agile Process Tool
A one-page canvas to manage Scrum agile projects.
[Learn more](#)

Scaled Scrum Process
LeSS and Nexus tools for managing scaled Scrum projects.
[Learn more](#)

User Story Mapping
Agile backlog and sprint tool for better management of PBIs.
[Learn more](#)

Quality Improvement
Chart and management tools that help you improve product quality.
[Learn more](#)

PM Diagrams and Charts
Visualize project roadmap and team structure with different charts.
[Learn more](#)

3

Introduction

◆ Visual paradigm also used for software architecture design

Full suite of Enterprise Architecture Tools

TOGAF, ArchiMate and more - All the EA tools that support enterprise architecture and digital transformation.

TOGAF ADM Tool
Industry unique TOGAF ADM Tool with actionable work items.
[Learn more](#)

DoDAF / NAF / MODAF
Develop and manage DoDAF / NAD / MODAF models through a grid view.
[Learn more](#)

Enterprise Modeling
Develop EA models with a certified ArchiMate modeling tool.
[Learn more](#)

Process Design
Visualize business processes with BPMN and document business rules.
[Learn more](#)

Process Improvement
Model as-is / to-be process and gap. Document improvement plan, KPI, etc.
[Learn more](#)

Customer Journey Map
Collect and analyze customers' behaviors, thoughts, and feelings.
[Learn more](#)

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R2 – Curriculum Design of the Course

www.bc4eco.eu

Introduction

◆ Provide Comprehensive DevOps Tool Suite

 Code Engineering

Generate and reverse code with model, for ORM, REST, etc.

[Learn more](#)

 Database Engineering

Generate, patch and reverse database with ERD.

[Learn more](#)

 UX Design

Visualize screen flow and layout with wireframe, storyboard, and prototype tool.

[Learn more](#)

 Use Case Management

Model document and manage project goals with use case tools.

[Learn more](#)

 Visual Modeling

Create UML, BPMN, DFD, ERD, SysML and SoAML models.

Data Flow Diagram (DFD)

- What is Data Flow Diagram?
- ❖ Data flow diagram (DFD) is a diagram being used frequently in software design.
 - ❖ visually represents the flow of data throughout processes in a given system.
 - ❖ DFD shows the kind of information that will be input to and output from processes as well as where the data will be stored.

Workflow diagram

- ❖ To visualize your process/workflow
- ❖ We need to know BPMN for process and workflow design
- ❖ Following tools are used for workflow/BPMN diagram

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Class Diagram

- ❖ In software engineering, a class diagram in the Unified Modeling Language (UML) is a type of static structure diagram that describes the structure of a system by showing the system's classes, their attributes, operations (or methods), and the relationships among objects.

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Component Diagram

- ❖ UML Component diagrams are used in modeling the physical aspects of object-oriented systems that are used for visualizing, specifying, and documenting component-based systems and also for constructing executable systems through forward and reverse engineering.
- ❖ Component diagrams are essentially class diagrams that focus on a system's components that often used to model the static implementation view of a system.

Communication Diagram

- ❖ UML communication diagrams, like the sequence diagrams - a kind of interaction diagram, shows how objects interact.
- ❖ A communication diagram is an extension of object diagram that shows the objects along with the messages that travel from one to another.
- ❖ In addition to the associations among objects, communication diagram shows the messages the objects send each other.

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Collaboration Diagram

- ❖ A Collaboration is a collection of named objects and actors with links connecting them. They collaborate in performing some task.
- ❖ A Collaboration defines a set of participants and relationships that are meaningful for a given set of purposes
- ❖ A Collaboration between objects working together provides emergent desirable functionalities in Object-Oriented systems
- ❖ Each object (responsibility) partially supports emergent functionalities
- ❖ Objects are able to produce (usable) high-level functionalities by working together
- ❖ Objects collaborate by communicating (passing messages) with one another in order to work together

Collaboration Diagram Example

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Thank you!

BC4
ECO

Second Day: Practical work

- ◆ Prototyping of architecture using Visual paradigm (Day Two)
- ◆ [School Collaboration System.vpd | Visual Paradigm Online \(visual-paradigm.com\)](#)

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Second Day

- ❖ Guided Technical Tutorial for Blockchain Implementation (Day Two)

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Appendix 14: Applied Blockchain Canvas

APPLIED BLOCKCHAIN CANVAS

Developed by R. Lyons, T. Margaria, S. Saay

Inspired by the Lean Blockchain model (<http://lean-blockchain.fr/>)

Appendix 15: Questionnaire, Module 1, Copenhagen Summer School.

Which university do you come from?

21 responses

On a scale from 1 to 5, how confident do you feel in developing conceptual solutions involving DLT or blockchain technologies?

21 responses

On a scale from 1 to 5, how knowledgeable are you now about UN Sustainable goals?

21 responses

On a scale from 1 to 5, how knowledgeable are you now about the Design Process and methods?

21 responses

On a scale from 1 to 5, how knowledgeable are you about Environmental challenges?

21 responses

Question: Can you give an example of a **fruitful** interdisciplinary exchange you had during the workshop?

Answers:

- Interdisciplinarity gave me an insight into what the others were doing, and the work went smoothly, with the ideas from everyone.
- I had great conversations with computer science-focused students on blockchain applications and potential pitfalls, which I had yet to consider.
- We were talking about how the different actors use the water. One of my group mates said, “But you are looking at this from a designer's perspective,” we started a debate. Then, we came to a consensus by looking at different perspectives: both a designer's perspective and the perspective of someone who studies sustainability and economics.
- Having people with different areas of study helped provide new ways of understanding and approaching the problem. It is essential when planning the implementation of the solution since it allows us to know how feasible the proposals are or if it is necessary to re-evaluate some of their practical aspects.

- I learned a lot about designing, but it is too complicated, and about blockchain, how and why use it is sometimes tough to accept
- It was great to hear about what kind of testing can be done to check the environment.
- It helped me to think from a different angle. Even though I still resist, I can consider it.
- An IT-related, technical mindset focuses on a zoomed, detailed solution design approach. This shows a new perspective to service designers, who often focus on a zoomed-out, holistic view.
- One of the group members in my group was highly skilled in working with blockchain. Without this group member, I would not have been able to work with creating a blockchain solution.
- Discussion of different problems from different angles.
- The same point from different angles - computer scientists, environmental engineers, and designers.
- It was interesting to witness the design students' thought processes.
- It was eye-opening listening to students from different fields. It broadened my perspective of how a team works.
- The design phase of the ideation was significant, as we had a fruitful interdisciplinary exchange. I had yet to learn how the design subject worked, but other group mates helped bring me up to speed.

Question: On a scale from 1 to 5, how relevant do you think a decentralised mindset is when addressing complex environmental challenges?

Answers:

- A decentralised mindset is relevant when addressing complex environmental challenges because it allows for more innovative, collaborative, and localised solutions better suited to these challenges with complexity and a need for **challenging power structures**.

- One person should not make the decisions; we should challenge power structures. The environment is something that affects everyone, so we shouldn't take into consideration the issues of only one party.
- We should think about everyone.
- It is essential that all stakeholders can be given a voice equally, as non-human entities can be. Thus, it is possible to analyse the problem extensively and solve it ethically without generating significant imbalances.
- The existing problems created with a system where one system manages all and seems it will not help much without being more transparent and accessible to all stakeholders.
- A decentralised mindset and product is not always the best option. Sometimes, centralised might be the better solution. It needs to be evaluated on a case-to-case basis.
- We should share the responsibility.
- Because it is transparent and distributed, data can be accessible anywhere in the world. We should not trust data centres.
- It means that all actors in an environmental challenge would have to have trust, which is unrealistic.
- Problems should be looked at from a deeper systemic level regarding how humans work and whether the structures we interact with daily are different.
- The answer above answers this question.

Question: On a scale from 1 to 5, how important is applying a decentralised mindset in your study/future profession? Why?

Answer:

- We depend on many intermediary actors, which can have bad results. **We need to be critical of the dynamics in those systems, and** decentralisation can solve this.

- It is essential to understand more miniature ecosystems and their actors and relationships, as no matter how centralised something is, there will always be decentralised elements.
- It is essential to decentralise to distribute the workload and responsibilities in a project. **A distributed and decentralised** mindset can help you generate a form of organisation that allows better feedback and indispensability between the parts of the project. However, it can be helpful to keep confident leaders to guide and focus on the group objective.
- Saving data and Traceability
- The benefits of having decentralised methods (thinking) could only add benefits **for complex challenges** (at least, that is what I think for now)
- It is good to have more views on things and **apply solutions that don't imagine** one stakeholder at the centre of everything.
- A decentralised mindset is crucial for creating a sustainable and equitable future in any profession. As an international business student, I have already integrated this ethos into my campus clothing swap service, which focuses on sustainability and community building.
- In computer science, it is suitable for storage effectiveness and relates similarly to designing solutions related to IoT.
- There will be decreased bureaucracy so that government services can use that money in other influential sectors.
- Many trust and transparency issues exist in the industries, especially within regulatory bodies and businesses with direct or indirect influence on the environment. Examples that come to mind include double counting in carbon trading and irresponsible parameter declaration regarding effluent wastewater and other emissions. Applying DLT could nip these problems in the bud by creating an avenue for trust and transparent data aggregation. Incorporating other infrastructure, such as IoTs, sensors, and blockchain-based data gateways, will be helpful, too.

Question: How did scan card activity affect your design process?

Answer:

- It was my first time using them, and I found them incredibly useful. And will be using them again.
- The scan cards gave us guiding ideas on what to focus on the assigned problem through practical examples.
- Having multiple sources of information was a great way to start the process and the conversation. Some people needed to learn about some subjects from the cards so we could explain them to each other.
- It gives a clue as to how the DLT can be utilised throughout different contexts.
- The scan cards helped us to talk about how blockchain can be used. But once again, it was beneficial to have a group member who could understand what the articles were about (and who was critical towards them).
- The process was split into steps, making it easy to understand the complete picture of the problem.
- They gave some interesting examples of blockchains, but some ideas were only conceptual, misleading, and too promising.
- It simplified the process, although confusing at first. At first, we went too broad, but we could work with the scan cards better once we specified scenarios.

Question: Can you name a very positive aspect of the workshop?

Answer:

- I am working with others who come from different study fields. Also, working with different cultures, everyone has a different aspect and helps you address a complex problem.
- The interdisciplinary teams
- I loved seeing the diversity of possibilities to face a common complex problem.
- Group working was the best.

- Intercountry craftsmanship. I loved hearing about other people's countries and having a dialogue with people who aren't studying in Denmark and service systems design. It helped broaden my perspectives.
- To be more critical of existing power dynamics in complex challenges forces you to demand more transparency, which helps you challenge hierarchies and power structures by eliminating them and thinking in a decentralised way (power elimination).
- They are experiencing how people with different professional backgrounds can bring other things.
- Working in an interdisciplinary team.
- Meeting different people from different backgrounds.
- The teachers were very knowledgeable and helpful.
- Collaborating with international students from multiple different disciplines. It opened up my mindset a lot, as hearing other people's perspectives on the challenge was fascinating.
- Teamwork and different ideas
- Interdisciplinary group

Appendix 16: Open ended questions, Module 2, Limerick Summer School.

What is your level of knowledge, experience or interest in - Blockchain technology?

- I have basic knowledge of blockchain technology and how it is used in software designs, cryptonomics, and financial transactions. Although I am yet to gain experience using blockchain technology, I would like to think of myself as teachable, a fast learner, and an inquisitive scientist which would be essential in working on a project inclusive of blockchain technology.

- I have a high interest in Blockchain technology; above-average knowledge of it with limited experience.
- I understand that blockchain is a decentralised digital ledger technology that allows for secure and transparent record-keeping of transactions. It has gained popularity in recent years due to its potential for applications in various industries such as finance, healthcare, and supply chain management.
- I have been interested and have studied this technology for the past three years. I am particularly intrigued by its potential to revolutionise healthcare by improving data security, interoperability, and patient privacy. It can also enable the secure and efficient sharing of healthcare data between patients, providers, and payers while ensuring data integrity and reducing costs. I am also exploring the idea of other use cases for blockchain in healthcare including medical record management, clinical trials, drug supply chain management, and insurance claim processing. Finally, I agree with the fact that blockchain technology can be utilised to address environmental challenges through the use of Distributed Ledger Technologies in a multi-disciplinary and innovative approach. The decentralised nature of blockchain can enhance transparency and accountability in environmental initiatives, while smart contracts can automate processes and ensure compliance with regulations.
- Basic knowledge of blockchain technology, interested in blockchain.
- Intermediate, Knows about the basic functionalities like for crypto and voting, how it works in backend, advantages like decentralisation, security and disadvantages like have a very bad impact on nature consumes a lot of energy per transaction since everybody in the system has to approve it #
- Foundational - basic understanding of its functionality and use cases, particularly in the context of humanitarian and developmental spheres.
- I don't have previous experience in Blockchain technology, but it is something I have been hearing about over time. I also recently started working on my masters dissertation, and it has to do with developing blockchain applications with low code platforms.

- Blockchain is a system used for recording information in a way that would be difficult to alter or hack the system. One of the key disadvantages would be if there would be a change required in the system it is very complex to change as the codes must be changed in each block.
- For the past six months I have developed a growing interest in Blockchain technology. I am aware that Blockchain technology involves a decentralised, immutable distributed ledger system that has the potential to revolutionise the public health sector.
- With its capacity to enhance data security, improve transparency, and enable interoperability, blockchain technology is poised to transform how public health data is collected, shared and used. Drawing on existing research and case studies, I have recently examined the potential applications of blockchain technology in public health, including disease surveillance, immunisation registries, supply chain management, and patient-centred care.
- Specifically, I am interested in blockchain technology and its potential applications in the public health sector. For instance, blockchain can be used to create a secure and transparent data sharing platform for disease surveillance, immunisation registries, and supply chain management. Moreover, I believe blockchain can empower patients to have control over their health data and enable patient-centred care. One of the main advantages of blockchain in the public health sector is its capacity to enhance data security.
- With blockchain, data is encrypted and stored in a decentralised ledger, making it difficult for unauthorised access or tampering. This can be particularly useful in disease surveillance, where timely and accurate data is critical to preventing and controlling outbreaks. Blockchain can also facilitate secure and transparent data sharing between public health agencies and healthcare providers, enabling faster response times and better outcomes.
- Limited experience as I have entered my Masters course straight from finishing my Undergraduate degree, however, I am very interested in the topic.

- Except I have some understanding on what is block chain and how it works and I have no deep knowledge or experience on it although I have masters of Biostatistics earlier. However, I am interested to gain more understanding on basics and how it works in this modern arena.
- Minimal knowledge
- Intermediate
- not applicable
- I have no direct experience with this technology but I am interested in learning how to implement it in areas of industrial chemistry. I understand that it is a data system that allows traceability of movements within a system of interest, so it has great potential to improve chemical processes on many levels.
- While I have no personal experience with Blockchain, I have a solid foundation in software engineering and an interest in learning more about cutting-edge technologies like Blockchain. I'm eager to learn more about its potential applications and how it could shape the future of various industries.
- I am very interested in Blockchain technology, when I was doing my bachelor's degree, I read some books about Blockchain technology.

What is your level of knowledge, experience or interest in - Environment/Sustainability?

- As an eco-friendly advocate, I am passionate about the replenishment of the green earth to provide a conducive and healthy living environment. I have worked on several projects on environment and sustainability in line with the United Nations global health Sustainable Development Goals during my masters program at the University of Limerick. Aside from having ample knowledge of the environmental challenges, I have gained experience in research, project planning and implementation, sustainable intervention programs, public health systems and promotion, Global health and sustainable development. I look forward to working with great minds around the world to bring about positive change in our environment.

- "I have always been interested in exploring the relationship between public health and environmental sustainability and to highlight its importance. Public health and environmental sustainability are two interrelated concepts that have gained increasing attention in recent years.
- My interest covers a broad area including topics such as air pollution, climate change, waste management, water quality, and sustainable development.
- It is my understanding that environmental factors, such as air pollution, water quality, and exposure to hazardous chemicals, can lead to a range of health problems, including respiratory and cardiovascular diseases, cancer, and neurological disorders. In addition, environmental degradation can affect the availability and quality of food, which can lead to malnutrition and related health problems. On the other hand, I have learned over the past few months as a postgraduate student, that public health interventions can contribute to environmental sustainability. For example, reducing carbon emissions can improve air quality and reduce the incidence of respiratory diseases. Promoting healthy and sustainable diets can reduce the environmental impact of food production and consumption. Moreover, public health approaches can facilitate the adoption of sustainable behaviours and lifestyles. Finally, I am interested in exploring further the role of public health professionals in promoting sustainable practices and policies to protect human health and the environment. "
- No experience related to sustainability
- "Pretty interested in the debate about technological development, environmental sustainability has to be compromised and vice versa. There should be a third option also where we take both of them together."
- Strong understanding of both environmental issues and subjects, and the overall elements of sustainability.
- I am very interested in learning about Environment and Sustainability and also working on projects related to it. However, I don't have a lot of experience in that area.

- Being conscious about nature and surroundings, I always look forward to reusing materials instead of disposing. Few of the examples would include turning glass bottles into light decoration items, candle glasses to beautiful pen stands , using fountain pens over normal pens, harvesting rainwater. I remember during my school days I won first place in the Inter school competition called "Gold from Waste " where my unique and innovative design of using old jeans and converting it to a shopping bag.
- "As a graduate of Zoology and now a postgraduate student of public health, I have a fair knowledge of the intersection of public health and environmental sustainability. As the global community faces increasing challenges posed by climate change and environmental degradation, the linkages between public health and environmental sustainability have become increasingly apparent, and my interest in this field of knowledge has improved tremendously.
- In recent years, the impact of environmental degradation on public health has become increasingly clear. Pollution, climate change, and other environmental factors are contributing to a range of health problems, from respiratory illnesses to malnutrition. At the same time, efforts to promote environmental sustainability are gaining momentum, as individuals, organisations, and governments seek to reduce their carbon footprint, protect natural resources, and promote sustainable practices. Against this backdrop, my research interests reflect my commitment to public health, as well as my growing interest in environment/sustainability by focusing on topics such as the impact of air pollution on health, the role of environmental factors in the spread of infectious diseases, and the potential for sustainable agriculture to improve nutrition and food security. These areas reflect my growing interest in the linkages between public health and environmental sustainability, and a desire to explore these linkages in greater depth."
- Sustainability is something which will be considered in all aspects of business going forward, therefore, I have a keen interest in ways in which we can improve sustainability for the future of the environment.

- As a public health student, I have median knowledge on environment/sustainability. I have also worked with different NGOs and personnel for analysing data related to environmental problems such as climate change effects, deforestation and others.
- Minimal knowledge (interest driven)
- High. I have done bachelors and masters in Energy Systems Engineering and i am continuing Phd Chemical Sciences in University of Limerick.
- Beginner
- Advanced level knowledge of Sustainable materials for energy storage devices.
- I am interested in the problem of pollution, especially the management of waste, both chemical and domestic. Through my career I know some protocols to mitigate water and soil contamination, and in turn, I have experienced the deficiencies that we have as a society/institutions to create strategies that solve this problem at its root. I am quite interested in helping to solve it with a frank and practical approach.
- "Having a software engineering background, I am convinced that technology can significantly help promote sustainability and reduce the impact on the environment, and I'm curious to learn how technology can help in this endeavour. I'm interested in finding out more information about the topic and its potential applications.
- The environment is crucial for our survival and well-being as humans. We rely on natural resources such as clean air, water, and food to sustain ourselves. If we don't take care of the environment, it can lead to a decline in these resources and ultimately impact our health and quality of life. Sustainability means living in a way that meets our current needs without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. It's important to prioritise sustainability to ensure a healthy and livable planet for ourselves and future generations.